

cascades

Cascading climate risks:
Towards adaptive and
resilient European Societies

Deliverable D4.2: Summary of findings for the Middle East and North Africa Case

Description:

This report surveys the likely and possible effects of climate change on the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) Region. It considers interactions between climate-related hazards, local human society and international systems, highlighting socio-political and economic conditions in the region that could shape future vulnerability and resilience. The report highlights several case-studies, drawing attention to the potential for ‘cascading risks’ which could transcend borders and affect Europe. These consider effects on health, livelihoods, delivery of basic services, and food security - and the implications these might have for economies, political stability, and the movement of people. Beyond reviewing existing literature, this report draws on the results of original research, including expert consultations and a scenario planning exercise with regional experts and stakeholders

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Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	6
1.1. CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE MENA	6
1.2. A DEEPLY TROUBLED REGION	6
1.3 GROWING ENGAGEMENT WITH ENVIRONMENTAL THREATS	7
1.4 EU ENGAGEMENT WITH THE REGION	7
1.5 METHODOLOGY	10
2. THE PRESENT: THE WATER, FOOD AND ENERGY NEXUS IN THE MENA REGION	12
2.1 THE WATER-FOOD-ENERGY NEXUS	14
2.2 EVIDENCE OF A CHANGING CLIMATE TODAY	16
3. CLIMATE CHANGE, EXPECTED BIOPHYSICAL IMPACTS AND RISK ANALYSIS	20
3.1 A SNAPSHOT OF THE REGION – 2030 TO 2050	21
3.2 WHAT COULD HAPPEN BEYOND 2050?	27
3.3. TRANSBOUNDARY EFFECTS	29
4. VULNERABILITY FACTORS	31
4.1 POLITICAL STABILITY	34
4.2 GOVERNANCE: EFFECTIVE AND INCLUSIVE INSTITUTIONS	36
4.3 GOVERNANCE: NON-STATE AND LOCAL EMPOWERMENT	40
4.4 ECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND WELL-BEING	42
4.5 ACCESS TO FINANCE AND TECHNOLOGY	47
4.6 DEMOGRAPHY	49
5. THE LIKELY EFFECTS OF CLIMATE IMPACTS ON HUMAN SOCIETIES AND SYSTEMS IN THE MENA	51
5.1 HUMAN HEALTH	52
5.2 LIVELIHOODS AND ECONOMIC OPPORTUNITIES	54
5.3 SOCIAL RELATIONS, COMMUNITIES AND RURAL-TO-URBAN MIGRATION	62
5.4 INSECURITY, CONFLICT AND CROSS-BORDER MIGRATION	67
6. RECOMMENDATIONS: WHAT SHOULD MENA GOVERNMENTS DO TO MEET CLIMATE-RELATED CHALLENGES AND HOW CAN GOVERNMENTS AND INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATIONS OUTSIDE THE REGION ASSIST THEM?	74
GENERAL RECOMMENDATIONS	75
APPENDIX .	82
SCENARIO 1: ‘STAGNATION’	82
SCENARIO 2: ‘FRAGMENTATION’	83
SCENARIO 3: ‘COOPERATION’	84
TABLE 3: REGIONAL PARAMETERS	86
INTERNATIONAL PARAMETERS	87
REFERENCES	88

List of Figures

Figure 1: Origin of agricultural imports to the MENA Region 2019	15
Box 1: Observed changes in the MENA between 1901 and 2013	17
Box 2: Changing of the seasons	18
Box 3: Tropical storm threats to life and infrastructure in Oman	18
Table 1: Effects in the MENA under selected IPCC climate pathways	21
Figure 2: Mean of daily average near-surface temperature	23
Figure 3: Mean of daily maximum near-surface temperature	24
Figure 4: Mean of annual precipitation	26
Figure 5: Sea-level projections for Tangier, Tunis and Alexandria	28
Box 4: Defining vulnerability	32
Figure 6: MENA 2019/2020 GDP per capita	33
Table 2: Summary of regional vulnerability/resilience factors and variables	34
Box 5: Damage vulnerability	37
Box 6: Shared Aquifer agreements	41
Figure 7: Agriculture's importance to the economy	46
Box 7: Worsening inequalities in the profit-led Tunisian olive sector	46
Figure 8: Economic dependence on hydrocarbons	50
Figure 9: Amount of climate finance approved for MENA recipient countries	52
Box 8: Future scenarios	54
Figure 10: Wet-bulb temperature extremes in the Arabian Gulf	56
Figure 11: Observed extreme humid heat in the Gulf region	56
Box 9: Food insecurity and job losses in the Maghreb	58
Figure 12: Climate risk cascade: Maghreb food security	60
Box 10: Infrastructure loss and damage in the GCC	63
Figure 13: Climate risk cascade: GCC	65
Box 11: West Bank de-development and inter-communal tensions	68
Figure 14: Climate risk cascade: Jordan Valley	70
Box 12: the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) and cascading climate risks	72
Figure 15: Climate risk cascade: Nile	74
Box 13: Iraq	75
Figure 16: Climate risk cascade: Iraq	76
Figure 17: Directional political scenarios for the MENA region 2025 – 2035	87
Table 3: Regional parameters	91

1. Introduction

1.1. Climate change in the MENA

Man-made environmental stresses and natural resource degradation in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region¹ already exacerbate human suffering. According to the World Resources Institute, of the world's 17 'extremely water stressed' countries, 11 are in the MENA region (Hofste et. al., 2019).² In 2040, with expected increases in population and business-as-usual extraction trends, the water situation in much of the region comes under extreme stress (World Resources Institute 2021). The region is doubly exposed to food security risks. The MENA region is the largest food importing region in the world. With reliance on imports from outside of the region for over 50 percent of calories consumed in most MENA nations (Mouël et al., 2016), countries will be exposed to the higher prices as a result of failed harvests and export bans elsewhere in the world which are anticipated as a result of climate change. Meanwhile, agriculture, which (including fisheries and forests) provides for 11% of employment and augments a tenuous level of food security and interregional trade, is under threat from the water situation. Heatwaves are also likely to have severe effects on human and animal health.

The region's rapidly expanding built environment – which includes buildings, roads, water, electricity, waste and industrial infrastructure is under threat from climate change, too. Flooding – already one of the most frequent environmental hazards in the region will continue to take lives, damage infrastructure and increase the risks of disease. Effects on rivers and groundwater, already over-exploited, have implications for rural to urban migration and food security. In other places, such as the Arabian Peninsula, new trends such as dust storms, tropical storms and sea-level rises will challenge vital infrastructure such as electricity, water and consequently, the economy.

1.2. A deeply troubled region

The MENA region faces special constraints and opportunities for resilience, given its geographic position and long-standing historical relationships with major powers including Europe and its reliance on a number of types of rent – oil and gas, security and aid. Securitized responses including new laws limiting freedoms, heavier policing of public space and cyber observation after the Iraq war in 2003 and since the Arab Spring in 2011 have tended to tighten the space for local and international civil society in the region (Battaloglu and Farasin, 2017; Knoope, 2018), weakening collaborative action on climate resilience and adaptation.

¹ The geographical area covered by this report is the MENA region as a whole, as defined by the US State Department: Algeria, Bahrain, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates and Yemen (US Department of State, 2021).

² The rating is given to countries where irrigated agriculture, industries and municipalities withdraw more than 80% of their available supply on average every year. Available supply refers to "renewable surface and ground-water supplies" which also take into account "the impact of upstream consumptive water users and large dams on downstream water availability" (WRI, 2019).

War damage and humanitarian crises arising from militarized conflict in Syria, Iraq, Libya, Yemen and Gaza in the last decade, the worsening conditions of occupation in Palestinian areas, governance breakdown and economic failure in Lebanon and the diplomatic tensions among Gulf countries continue to overshadow environmental and climate challenges. From the destruction of water facilities, housing and schools to the soil, water and air pollution from makeshift refineries and bombs, conflict is negatively impacting on the environment, increasing vulnerability to a host of health impacts and climate change. This becomes evident for example from the death toll from flooding in Yemen and the poisoned land which cannot be used for food growing in Northern Syria (Zwijnenberg et. al. 2021). As of 2020, the UNHCR estimated 10.3 million displaced people, 2.7m refugees and 2.3 million returnees in the region, the majority of whom face the challenges of insecure shelter, constrained access to resources and means of income generation (UNHCR, 2020a). In addition, there are over five million Palestinian refugees registered with UNRWA, around 1.5 million of whom live in camps which have become “hyper-congested masses of multi-storey buildings with narrow alleys, characterized by high concentrations of poverty and extreme overcrowding” (UNRWA, no date).

With respect to climate impacts, states of conflict and the fallout of conflict both create conditions of increased vulnerability and can accentuate and further transmit risks, further elaborated in section 4. Climate factors can also interact with local frustrations, potentially playing a driving role in conflict as will be explored in section 5.

1.3 Growing engagement with environmental threats

However, the last decade has also witnessed the growth of environmental movements in the MENA region, louder voices on climate change and increasing recognition from many governments of the need to tackle environmental problems and rework policies to enable access to climate finance. Catastrophic events including the Jeddah floods and the tropical storms that hit the Omani coastline have spurred both grassroots environmental movements and wider early warning systems and climate strategies. Since Qatar hosted the COP in 2012, there has also been a visible change in the positions of some of the major oil exporters in terms of recognizing the vulnerability of their economic models and seizing opportunities to invest in infrastructure for a more sustainable future. Since 2015, most countries in the region have ratified the Paris Agreement and submitted Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). However, the region notably holds four of the six countries globally that have not: Iraq, Iran, Libya and Yemen. Hence these countries do not have an NDC.

1.4 EU engagement with the region

Europe and MENA are historically and economically intertwined. If taken as a single entity, Europe was the MENA region’s largest trading partner between 2014 and 2017 with \$637 billion trade in goods and services (ECFR, 2019). Many European companies are invested in infrastructure and business in the region – between 2014 and 2017, EU foreign direct investment totalled around \$292 billion (Zarhloule, 2019) - and Europe contributes substantially to humanitarian relief and development operations. In 2019, EU institutions and EU countries together provided the region (as defined in our report) with \$2.33 billion for humanitarian relief and \$7.77 billion in ODA (OECD, 2019). These

humanitarian relief numbers are higher when one includes going to Turkey, Greece and Italy as the first receivers of migrants coming from or through the MENA region. Migration from and through the MENA region into Europe has increased significantly with the onset of the Syria crisis in 2011 with Europe now hosting about one third of all people migrating from MENA countries including some 4.9 million Syrian refugees (International Organization for Migration, 2016).

The EU and EU development banks have become prominent contributors to climate resilience capacity-building and projects in the Mediterranean region (which includes countries sharing the Mediterranean coastline as well as Jordan) with a strong focus on energy and water security. There are also several bilateral technical assistance partnerships between EU and MENA governments which focus on these areas, particularly Germany's GIZ and Sweden's SIDA.

Climate change and the environment also present areas for peace-building and longer-term cooperation as there are shared interests in shared resources. Several European organizations including the EU, SIPRI, PAX³ and the Finish, Dutch and Swedish governments have supported various environmental peace-building initiatives. While evidence of countries putting this into action is currently lacking, we identify areas where it could play a positive role in future.

Based on the available literature, climate impact data analysis and a series of interviews and workshops with regional experts, this report surveys the range of potential climate impacts on the MENA region. It focuses on how these might compound with each other and with socio-political and environmental factors on the ground. The focus on countries will not be equal but will attempt to capture dynamics and cascading effects that will help enable understanding of how resilience and adaptive actions might help to mitigate risks and limit the scope of harm that climate impacts could set in motion.

The study will summarize the answers to the following questions:

- How is climate change projected to affect the region?
- What are the main biophysical impacts which are projected?
- How vulnerable are MENA countries to climate change impacts?
- How would these impacts affect health, economies, livelihoods, social cohesion, internal political stability, security and foreign relations? And how might these effects cascade to impact Europe?
- What might MENA countries and external partners, the EU in particular, do to increase resilience and adapt in the face of these impacts?

The report identifies specific resilience and adaptation priorities in the areas of **improving water management** is a theme that runs through each of these, followed

³ SIPRI is the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute working on conflict and arms control since 1966; PAX is a Dutch NGO focused on peace working in the Middle East since the 1990s.

by **regeneration of landscapes** and **built infrastructure resilience**. It argues that these cannot be achieved without acting within the wider political and economic context to strengthen sustainable peace and good governance. Exploring future scenarios (explained in Appendix 1 and drawn on in Section 5) could be useful, not only in understanding how vulnerable MENA societies will be to climate impacts, but also how work on climate resilience and adaptation itself might help foster the preferred scenario.

With respect to EU action in the region, the report identifies 6 areas broad areas which should inform the EU's approach to resilience and adaptation in the region:

1. Taking advantage of its role as a major trading partner to the region to push for regional peace and cooperation through alignment with its Green Deal.
2. Providing Climate Change modelling tools for national and local scenario building and further assistance with monitoring and early warning systems for climate-related and compound hazards.
3. Finding ways in which remedial and post-conflict rehabilitation work can help address humanitarian needs whilst fostering long term environmental resilience.
4. Building climate resilience in cities and subnational areas of the MENA region by developing technical capacity to address climate related issues and manage water-energy-food (WEF) nexus.
5. Paying close attention to mechanisms to scale up sustainable finance taking into account the effectiveness of centralized bureaucracies versus local agencies and other actors in the area concerned.
6. Using financial instruments for climate resilience and adaptation to help to empower local actors and build better national to sub-national linkages.

1.5 Methodology

This report uses a mixed methods approach, combining qualitative literature review, analysis⁴ and visualisation of climate impact projections from the ISIMIP⁵ project, semi-structured interviews, as well as a participatory scenario planning exercise conducted with regional experts. Desk research included academic papers, grey literature, technical reports, and policy briefs, in order to prepare for semi-structured interviews with experts and stakeholders. Partners in the project – researchers from Chatham House, the West Asia and North Africa Institute and ECDPM conducted a total of 28 interviews with regional experts - 10 conducted by ECDPM (in French), 10 conducted by Chatham House (in English) and 7 by the WANA Institute (in Arabic and English) and 1 jointly using Zoom. 10 of these interviews were used to help draw up ‘cascade’ diagrams, drawing attention to specific sub-regional risks. Together, we organized a workshop in two parts, using an online roundtable format i) 2 mornings focusing on testing climate risk cascades and developing scenarios for non-climate factors affecting the region (see section 5 for a further explanation of these scenarios and the risk cascades) and ii) 2 mornings focusing on resilience and adaptation measures. We used *Miroboard* and real time *Mentimeter* surveys to capture participant’s input throughout. Great care was taken to recruit participants from the three countries and from diverse professional backgrounds (e.g. academics, policymakers and advocates, as well as development and security sector practitioners).

The exercise resulted in the development of three scenarios for the region for the year 2050. The scenarios are not exhaustive but rather meant to offer insights into different plausible futures and to inform policies and adaptation strategies

The report focuses on the projected and potential impacts of climate change on societies in the MENA region, in particular how physical risks translate into socio-political, economic and security risks within and across borders. It does not consider the contribution (both actual and potential) of MENA countries to global climate change and the mitigation thereof. The time-horizons used in the literature for plotting climate change impacts on the region vary. For this reason, we have split the future impacts into those we are seeing now (in the now to 2030 time-frame), those 2030 to 2050 and those beyond 2050. We refer frequently to the IPCC’s Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) which are scenarios based on radiative projections of forcing. In particular, we focussed on the stringent GHG emissions reduction scenario, “*likely* below 2°C” (RCP2.6), an intermediate one where emissions decline slowly (RCP 4.5) and the unabated high emissions one (RCP8.5) (IPCC, 2014).⁶ Given the novelty of the RCP 1.9 scenario, which assumes a mitigation pathway compatible with 1.5 degrees, there is not much to draw upon from the literature but we can assume that impacts under

⁴ Through maps, figures, and descriptive statistics that are partly shown in this report.

⁵ The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP) “offers a framework for consistently projecting the impacts of climate change across affected sectors and spatial scales. An international network of climate-impact modellers contribute to a comprehensive and consistent picture of the world under different climate change scenarios” (<https://www.isimip.org/>).

⁶ For a clear explanation see the primer on Mitigation from climatescenarios.org <https://climatescenarios.org/primer/mitigation/>

this scenario will be similar to around mid century, given the level of warming already locked in, but extremes would be limited from there on.

Climate and other environmental risks are not uniform across the region in their degree of severity; nor are they uniform in terms of their likely economic, social and political impacts, bearing in mind the capacity of the states concerned to respond to them. For the purposes of this case study, we consider *exposure* – the biophysical exposure to climate change which takes into account the areas affected that are important to human society; and the *risks*, based on *vulnerability* of the area and society – considering a system’s sensitivity to the changes and its adaptive capacity. As vulnerability is a complex issue, and essential to define prior to thinking about resilience and adaptation measures, we go into more detail on how we can understand vulnerability in the MENA region. This report is limited in scope, and focuses on those risks understood to have the strongest impact on Europe and EU interests.

The common language of 1.5, 2 or 4 degrees of average temperature change over pre-industrial levels fails to capture the volatility and extremes in climate that these moderate-sounding changes imply. As the first comprehensive assessment of climate change impacts in the Arab region puts it, “changes in extreme weather events are sometimes even more important, as they can have severe impacts on human health, built infrastructure, the natural environment, the transportation sector and the economy at large.”(UNESCWA et al., 2017).

The effects of climate change in other parts of the world and the responses to these that could affect the region will also be considered here, most notably food price shocks and changes in demand for oil and gas. Scientists are also advancing understanding of climate ‘tipping points’, low probability, potentially high impact events which could cause drastic global weather changes and/or biodiversity loss and speed up warming (Lenton et al., 2019). While the specific effects of these are not dealt with here, it is important to bear in mind their effects – particularly on global food production - which could intensify global changes which in turn affect the MENA through transmission mechanisms such as trade.

2. The present: the water, food and energy nexus in the MENA region

The MENA is the driest of the world's major regions and has for many years been using more water than is naturally renewed – for example, by over-drawing from aquifers or by increasing the supply of water through desalination. According to the ranking of baseline water stress published by the WRI (World Resources Institute), all 18 MENA countries suffer from “extremely high” (11) or “high” (seven) baseline water stress (“the ratio of total water withdrawals to available renewable water supplies”) (World Resources Institute, 2021).

In many parts of the region, rainfall is not sufficient for rain-fed (that is, un-irrigated) agriculture, which normally requires annual rainfall of around 200-250 mm. Even where the average annual rainfall is high enough for rain-fed agriculture, it is still a precarious business, given the variability in rainfall from year to year (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2021). Rain-fed farming is nonetheless important for around 70 percent of the region's cropland area (The World Bank Group, 2014).

The opportunities for the expansion of food production within the region using current practices are limited. Irrigated agriculture accounts for more than 50 percent of total agricultural production in the region (The World Bank Group, 2014) and this uses around 85% of the region's water (Zafar, 2021). There is no unexploited water that could be used to expand production. Indeed, almost all water resources are already over-used. The Nile, the Jordan and many other regional rivers are “closed basins”, with no unallocated water remaining, and many aquifers continue to be exploited beyond natural rates of replenishment (Hoff et al., 2012). Jordan's Ministry of Water, for example, has estimated that groundwater is being pumped at twice the rate at which it is being replenished (Whitman, 2019). This over-exploitation of ground-water reserves means that they are less and less able to perform their traditional function as “buffers” during times of less rainfall and reduced river flows (The World Bank Group, 2014).

Allocating more water to irrigation at the expense of other uses is not an economically attractive option, given that those other uses (industry, commerce, tourism, domestic use etc) offer much higher economic returns per cubic metre of water.

Food consumption and nutrition varies vastly across the region. Well over half of Yemen's population are food-insecure and one in five children suffer from malnourishment while over a third of adults in Kuwait, Jordan, Saudi Arabia and Qatar are classed as obese⁷ (AlAbdulKader 2019, citing WHO 2016 data, Nahhas, 2017). Obesity can also go hand in hand with undernourishment, cause chronic inflammation and increase the risk of a number of illnesses including cardiovascular, diabetes and respiratory diseases.

Between the end of the Second World War and the 1990s, the larger countries in the region variously pursued agricultural self-sufficiency policies (Egypt, Syria and the Arabian Peninsula countries from the 1950s and Iran following the 1979 revolution for

⁷ For comparison, globally, 13 percent of the population are classed as obese.

example), often subsidizing inputs to agriculture and offering secure prices for farmers (although this varied from country to country). However, a combination of increasing 'rents' (e.g. oil, security, aid) increasing foreign currency, food subsidies, rapidly-growing populations, structural adjustment accompanied by liberalization policies, changing dietary habits and the mounting stress on water resources has led most countries to import increasing amounts.

Iran is the exception, given the decades of sanctions imposed upon it. Iran has prioritized national food production and relies on imports for only about 25 percent of its food consumption. However, sanctions clearly affected food security in the country and demonstrates sensitivity to supply constraints. According to one study, the reimposition of US sanctions in 2018 increasing the "annual average cost of a healthy diet for a sample Iranian family" 3.6 times compared with the previous year (Hejazi and Emamgholipour, 2020).

According to the World Bank, "Approximately 50 percent of regional wheat and barley consumption, 40 percent of rice consumption, and nearly 70 percent of maize consumption is met through imports" (The World Bank Group, 2014). In 2019, the cost of agricultural imports (primary food and fodder and live animals) from outside the region in 2019 totalled USD81 billion. Around 36% of that bought cereal grains, sugar and rice while meat, poultry, dairy and animal feed (including soybeans) accounted for about 28%.

Agricultural imports come chiefly from the EU, Brazil, India, Argentina, the US, Turkey, Russia and Ukraine (Chatham House, 2020). In the literature, this is often referred to as the import of "virtual water", meaning the water which was used to produce the food in other countries (Allen, 2001). This cost is easily borne by countries that earn large sums by exporting hydrocarbons, less by those that do not. Egypt, which falls into the latter category, is the world's largest grain-importing country (Babar and Mirgani, 2014).

Figure 1: Origin of agricultural imports to the MENA Region 2019
Note: this map includes Turkey and Sudan within the MENA which this study does not, hence the figures given in the text are different. Source: Chatham House Resource Trade Database, <https://resourcetrade.earth/>

2.1 The water-food-energy nexus

Water, energy and food security are tightly connected and climate change creates new conditions for all three areas. In the MENA region, that nexus plays out in specific ways which will be key to the discussion of climate impacts and risks.

Irrigation for crops

Cheap local production of fuel and/or subsidies and generally unregulated, unpriced water, have encouraged the expansion of unsustainable water pumping and irrigation to take place in most countries across the region. The availability of cheap diesel to power pumps in tube wells has enabled the exploitation of the deeper parts of aquifers, in turn enabling increased production of crops, but at the cost of depleting aquifers. It is remarkable for example that Saudi Arabia was the sixth largest wheat exporter in

the world in the mid-1990s, while its groundwater resources have reduced rapidly since oil-enabled, mechanized agriculture began to take off in the early 1980s.⁸ Yemen's groundwater has also rapidly depleted over the last 40 years, with the increase of water-intensive *qat* growing - consumption of which and the deployment of diesel pumps were also initially fostered by the oil boom in neighbouring countries and increasing remittances (McCracken, 2012).

Water for electricity

The use of river water to produce energy through damming and hydroelectric plants affects agricultural production. River water is used to generate power in a number of locations, such as the Aswan High Dam (Egypt), Tabqa Dam (Syria), Mosul and Darbandikhan Dams (both in Iraq) and the Seimare Dam (Iran). The damming involved in hydropower plants affects the flow of rivers and also leads to increased evaporation (Moran et al., 2018). For example, in Iran, it was estimated in 2011 that "dams are one of the main factors leading to environmental degradation of aquatic ecosystems and to the evaporation of about 5 billion cubic meters of renewable water" Hoominfar and Radel, 2020 citing PurQiyomi et. al., 2011). Iraq is estimated to lose around 8 billion cubic meters of water each year in evaporation, due to reservoirs and damming (Cooke et. al. 2020). Damming can also compete directly with agriculture by flooding farmland and through filling with water during growing seasons and also increase upstream evaporation. As rivers often run across borders, such activities can become issues for cross-border tension as discussed in 3.3. For example, in 2018, the filling of the Ilusu dam in Turkey led the Iraqi government to put a ban on rice growing due to the reduced river flow. Mueller et. al., 2021 explain these dynamics in detail with respect to the Euphrates and Tigris rivers.

Energy for potable water

Energy is also used to treat and distribute water - and in some regions, to produce freshwater from sea-water through desalination. In Jordan for example, the Water Authority accounts for around 14 percent of total electricity consumption (Lahn et. al. 2016). The greater the demand for fresh water in agriculture, the greater the pressures to secure alternative sources for urban use.

Desalination is most prevalent in the Gulf Arab states but is increasingly significant for Iran, which is planning huge project to transfer desalinated water from the Persian Gulf and the Oman Sea to its central plateau and eastern regions, and for Israel and Jordan where the stressed Jordan River and other fresh water sources are failing to meet needs. Without desalination, the present levels of population in the Gulf states would be untenable. However, the process is not cost free in environmental terms: the burning of oil and gas to produce water through desalination contributes to global warming and the by-product (concentrated brine) alters the ecology of the sea around the desalination plant. In the GCC countries, the share of total oil and gas consumption used for desalination was estimated to range between 10% in Saudi Arabia and around

⁸ A study made in 2004 based on government data estimated that reserves of non-renewable groundwater (estimates differ significantly) could run out between 2026 and 2042 at levels of extraction at the time (Elhadj, 2004).

30% in Qatar and UAE in 2013 (Lahn et al., 2013). These countries are increasingly investing in solar powered reverse osmosis plants to reduce the call on fuel and increase efficiency of the process. The Emirate of Dubai for example, is aiming to power 100% of its desalination plants using solar power by 2030 (Hawa, 2020).

Energy for farm to fork

As is the case globally, energy and potable water are required in the transportation, preparation and storage of food. In the MENA region, few options of rail or waterway means that transportation depends heavily on roads and diesel fuel. Liquid petroleum gas (LPG)/butane is the most common form of cooking fuel across the region. Cooling and refrigeration are powered by electricity, still chiefly generated by oil and gas across the region. In some areas, particularly refugee and internal displacement camps and places affected by conflict, lack of refrigeration and unreliable or expensive cooking fuel supplies can jeopardize food security, exacerbating poverty and malnutrition.

Fuel revenues for food

12 of the 18 countries that we are covering in the region depend on oil and gas exports for the foreign exchange that allows them to import current volumes of food. Revenues from the oil and gas sector have also allowed some countries – particularly in the GCC and Iraq - to guarantee purchases, offer agricultural insurances and subsidize food directly (Bailey and Willoughby, 2013) and to invest in agricultural land abroad (discussed in Section 4). More recently Algeria has begun offering incentives for investment in agriculture in a quest for reduced import dependence, partly because of its difficulties in paying for rising imports, given falling oil revenues and growing consumption from urban areas (Oirere, 2021).

2.2 Evidence of a changing climate today

There are multiple indications that the region’s climate has already begun to change (although it is difficult to judge the extent to which patterns of weather observed in recent decades have been due to climate change and which to natural variation (Selby et al., 2017) Box 1 explains the small but significant increases in average mean temperature and reductions in rainfall.

Box 1: Observed changes in the MENA between 1901 and 2013

The GERICS Climate-Fact-Sheets for the Levant (Jordan, Lebanon, Palestine, Syria and Israel) and Egypt, based on a review of the literature available in 2015, state that a “small but significant increase” in temperature was observed for the period between 1901 and 2013 (+0.11°C per decade for the Levant, 0.07°C for Egypt), with a greater increase (0.4°C and 0.53°C per decade respectively) over the last 30 years (Rechid, 2015). In Iran, annual mean temperature has risen by about 0.3°C/decade over the last 50 years, especially in the eastern parts of the country (Rahimi et al., 2019).

Over the same 113-year period, there was a “small but significant” fall in precipitation (-4%/30 years for the Levant, -6%/30 years for Egypt), again with a stronger effect observable over the last 30 years (-11%/30 years and -22%/30 years respectively).

Moreover, a reduction of 12% in available freshwater since the 1970s was estimated for the coastal zone of the Levant, where 60% of the population of this sub-region live.⁹

Most significantly for agriculture, **many rural regions note the changes that have taken place in the seasons**, with a more abrupt shift from winter to summer, and a shortening of the growing season (see box 2). Salinization of coastal groundwater aquifers is increasing as depletion due to damming, diversions and unsustainable uses combines with climatic change (Abulibdeh et al., 2021). In parts of Oman for example, vegetation is turning brown from the increasingly saline water, causing the abandonment of farms.¹⁰

Box 2: Changing of the seasons

Climate change is exacerbating existing environmental pressures, particularly on water and delicate ecosystems which are at risk in several parts of the country. A shortening of the growing season is one already notable impact across the region, expected to influence future food production (Choudri et al., 2013). The 2019 IPCC Climate Change and Land report drew attention to the threat of climate change oasis systems and agricultural areas in the Arabian Peninsula, particularly the effects of “strong decreases in winter chill” affecting well-established species (Mirzabaev et al., 2019). The risk of detrimental chill shortfalls is expected to increase gradually, slowly diminishing the economic prospects to produce such species. The last 2 decades have already seen severe reductions in fruit tree production in the high mountain oases of Al-Jabal Al-Akhdar (literally, ‘the green mountain’). The abundance of temperate zone (Mediterranean) fruit and nuts fell by between 86 and 100% during certain years, potentially due to the warmer winters (Mirzabaev et al., 2019; Al-Kalbani et al., 2014; Al-Kalbani et al., 2016). A 2013 study of farmers north of Muscat in (the next most populous) Al-Batinah governorate noted that they were active in adaptive practices from crop changes to water conservation in response to these changes and are also “diversifying from farm to non-farm activities” (Choudri, Al-Busaidi and Ahmed, 2013).

Higher maximum temperatures in summer are noticeable in the last few years, with record heat waves. This is challenging both for outside manual and animal labour, for evaporation and for the health of plants themselves (Nievola et al., 2017). Ocean ecosystems are also at risk from warming. A 2020 study observed an increase in surface sea temperatures (SSTs) by 0.7 °C per decade along the western side of the Gulf, suggesting that it could be above the tolerance limit of coral reefs. In the Gulf, SSTs have increased to the extent that bleaching of coral is observable in seven locations (Hereher, 2020). At the same time, “dead zones”, where lack of oxygen makes areas uninhabitable for most sea-life, specifically in the area between Oman and Iran, appear to be deepening and widening as the warming of sea increases (Phys.org, 2018 check). Another feature of seasonal change is the record breaking periods of freezing temperatures across the Levant (Salameh et al, 2019).

⁹ The GERICS Climate-Fact-Sheet for Egypt does not offer an equivalent figure. In Iran, annual precipitation has slightly decreased, by 7 mm/decade (Rahimi et al., 2019).

¹⁰ Comment made during the regional expert interviews.

Another sign of a change in the region's climate is the increased frequency in the occurrence of cyclones. Cyclone Gonu, which struck Oman in 2007, was particularly violent but several cyclones have hit Oman since (see box 3) (Guy, Miller and Khan, 2019). The majority of the population and built-up areas are spread out along the flat area by the coast below a low mountain range so exposure to cyclones as well as flooding is high.

Box 3: Tropical storm threats to life and infrastructure in Oman

In the last 2 decades, Oman has witnessed changes in its historical monsoon season, with increased frequency of cyclones. In June 2007, a super cyclone - Gonu - hit the Sea of Oman and the coastal areas. *"This cyclone is the strongest on record in the Arabian Sea, with 900 mm of rain falling on a single day (5 June 2007) and average wind speeds reaching about 130 km/h."* (Al-Awadhi et al., 2018) 50 people died as a result of the storm and economic losses were estimated at US\$4.2 billion. In 2010, Cyclone Phet caused the death of 21 people in Oman, in 2011, Tropical Storm Keila caused 12 (Ministry of Transport and Communications, Oman, 2012)¹¹, both causing significant damage to bridges, roads, desalination plants, electricity and water pipes and economic losses. At the end of October 2019 another supercyclone (Cyclone Kyarr) reached a peak of around 250kmph (155mph) in the Arabian Sea (Gonu reached a peak of 270kmph) but avoided the Omani coast. Kyarr was the 4th typhoon strength storm in the Indian Ocean basin in 2019, the most ever recorded by October (Guy et al., 2019). Studies have attributed this trend to climate change and expect increased severity with global warming (Murakami et al., 2017).

Flooding

Some countries in the region are prone to flooding and the incidence of damaging flood events seems to be increasing. Yemen, perhaps the worst affected country in the region, suffered 19 floods or flash floods over the two decades up to 2013. In 2020, torrential rains and severe flash floods combined with the fallout of conflict to create a humanitarian disaster. An estimated 300,000 people lost their homes, crops and livestock and at least 148 people died in two months (UNHCR, 2020b). Floods have also caused damage and loss of life elsewhere, for example, in Jeddah in Saudi Arabia (in 2009, 2011 and 2017) and in Israel and Jordan in 2018. Horizontal expansion of the urban areas along coastlines in some of the Gulf states have increased exposure. Building on *wadis* (main channels for outflow of water to the ocean) has contributed to the extreme flash flooding in Muscat and Jeddah for example, exacerbated by the lack of sewerage and storm drainage systems.

Sea level rise is also an increasing concern for coastal areas. In the eastern Mediterranean, a rise in sea-level of about 1.4mm per year has been recorded since 1955 (Rechid, 2015) [GERICS]. Although this is not yet having a noticeable effect, it

11

threatens artificial islands such as the Dubai Palm Island (Mulhern, 2020), fisheries such as those on the Red Sea coast in Egypt, and low-lying coastal regions such as the tourist areas of Oman.

Human interaction with climate change

As is clear from the examples given above, local human impacts such as the density of population, overgrazing and monocropping, urban build up, damming, land reclamation and destruction of natural barriers such as mangroves and deforestation affect the vulnerability and severity of impact of climate-related events. At the same time, restoring ecosystems can play a role in helping to regulate climates at the local level, for example, trees play a role in providing shading, enhancing soil stability and in groundwater recharge, as will be elaborated in Section 6.

3. Climate change, expected biophysical impacts and risk analysis

Given cumulative emissions to date, climate science suggests that average temperatures will continue to rise to around the mid-2040s on current trajectories. We therefore consider the period from now until around 2045 as ‘locked-in’. Climate change in the MENA region is therefore likely to continue, although regional actions may influence how harshly this is felt in local weather conditions. Current global emissions mitigation actions have the potential to influence which of the projected climate pathways may become reality from the mid-2040s onward. Bearing this in mind, we summarize some of the key trends identified in existing literature.

From 2050 onwards, we can consider the IPCC’s Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) which plot alternative emissions trajectories, with the best case (2.6) seeing emissions peak in 2020 and the worst where emissions continue to grow (8.5). The table below gives a summary of how the MENA region could be affected under RCP2.6, RCP4.5, in which emissions peak around 2050 and decline rapidly thereafter, and the worst case, RCP 8.5.

RCP/ Year	2.6	4.5	8.5
2050		Av. temp. higher by 1.2-1.9 ⁰ C over the 1986 -2005 period. More very hot days. Mountain snowpacks melt earlier in the year. Reduced precipitation over most of the region but more frequent and more intense rainfall events. Storms (inc. dust storms and cyclones) occur more often.	Av. temp. higher by 1.7-2.6 ⁰ C over the 1986 to 2005 period. Mountain snowpacks melt earlier in the year. Lower precipitation over most of the region but more frequent and more intense rainfall events. Storms (inc. dust storms and cyclones) occur more often. Some coastal locations will be at risk because of SLR and associated storm surges.
2100	Warming of around 1.8 to 2 ^o C Less than 30 days of at least moderate drought conditions on average every year in 2080-2100 Sea-level rise of about 0.35m, with a maximum of 0.6m	Highly unusual heat extremes may occur in 30% of summer months. Most parts of the region will be drier than in 2050 (precipitation and soil moisture both lower). SW Arabian Pen. will be wetter, causing more flooding. SLR and associated storm surges will affect some coasts.	Unprecedented heat extremes in 80% of summer months. May be >200 heatwave days per year.. Most parts of the region will be much drier than in 2050 (and much drier than 2100 under RCP 4.5). SW Arabian Pen. will have more frequent and more intense rainfall events, causing severe flooding. SLR and associated storm surges will affect most coasts.

Table 1: Effects in the MENA under selected IPCC climate pathways
Source: Collated from the literature

In considering the material presented in this section, readers should be aware that baseline periods used by studies are sometimes different, as are the time-horizons adopted.

Data and projections for Iran may not be as reliable as those for other parts of the region (Vaghefi et al., 2019).

3.1 A snapshot of the region – 2030 to 2050

The MENA region will become hotter and drier over the next 20 years, but with variation between regions in both precipitation patterns and temperature extremes.

The ISIMIP maps (figures 2 and 3) below show the projected average annual temperature increases over the next 30 years. Keeping emissions within 1.5 degree target - which is not modelled here, given the newness of that scenario (RCP 1.9) - would further limit increases. However, cumulative emissions will mean that warming will continue on a path to around mid-century. The warming effect will be stronger in summer than in winter. The number of very hot days will increase (Driouech *et al.*, 2020).

As far as extreme temperatures are concerned, it is clear that the science has been conservative; Lelieveld *et al.*, 2014 wrote that “the maximum temperature during the hottest days in the recent past was about 43°C, which could increase to about 46°–47 °C by mid-century.” Maximum temperatures in the region are already exceeding 50°C in some interior regions of Arabian Gulf countries. Certain areas are likely to experience more extended periods of such extreme maximum temperatures. For example, in the southern part of Iran, which is already suffering heavily from droughts (Vaghefi et al., 2019).

RCP 2.6

RCP 6.0

RCP 8.5

Figure 2: Mean of daily average near-surface temperature (degrees C): difference between 1991-2020 and 2021-2050 under RCP 2.6, 6.0 and 8.5 projections
Source: ISIMIP

RCP 2.6

RCP 6.0

RCP 8.5

Figure 3: Mean of daily maximum near-surface temperature (degrees C): difference between 1991-2020 and 2021-2050 under RCP 2.6, 6.0 and 8.5 projections
 Source: ISIMIP

More specifically, for the Levant (Jordan, Lebanon, Palestine, Syria, Israel), it is “likely” that annual average temperatures will be 1.2-1.9°C higher by 2030 and 1.7-2.9°C higher by 2050 (...), relative to a 1971-2000 baseline (Rechid, 2015). Similar figures apply to Egypt. For some places in the Gulf (Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Doha, Dhahran and Bandar Abbas) the wet-bulb temperature is projected to exceed 35°C several times in the 2071-2100 period. (A wet-bulb temperature of 35°C represents “the level at which

prolonged exposure becomes intolerable” (Pal and Eltahir, 2016; Regional Integrated Sciences and Assessments Programme, 2020).

Precipitation is more challenging to project across the region than temperature, the various models do not always agree. Depending on which model is chosen, there is more variation from place to place in the region. Iran is projected to experience extended periods of dry as well as wet conditions, with a higher frequency of floods (Vaghefi et al., 2019). For Arab countries “[d]ecreasing trends can be seen” (ESCWA et al., 2017, p. 89). The ISIMIP maps in figure 4 show possible changes in annual average precipitation but not the seasonal differences which may account for the lack of change across North Africa. Some parts of the region are projected to experience particularly heavy reductions in precipitation in winter (December-February). This effect will be more noticeable for example in the Atlas Mountains in Morocco and in northern Algeria and elsewhere along the Mediterranean coast than in other parts of the region.

RCP 2.6

RCP 6.0

RCP 8.5

Figure 4: Mean of annual precipitation (mm/a): difference between 1991-2020 and 2021-2050 under RCP 2.6, 6.0 and 8.5 projections

Source: ISIMIP

The reliability of rainfall from year to year seems likely to decrease too (that is, its variability will increase), although the literature is uncertain about the greater likelihood of longer runs of drought years (that is, more dry years in each run of dry years).

This picture of generally declining precipitation does not hold for the entire MENA region. In the southern parts of Algeria, Libya, Egypt and the Arabian Peninsula there

may be increases in precipitation. However, given that these are desert regions that register very little precipitation in the current climate, these increases do not offer much in terms of economic opportunities (ESCWA et al., 2017, p. 104).

While precipitation will be lower over much of the region, intense rainfall events will become even more intense and occur more often, causing more frequent and more destructive flooding. This flooding may trigger landslides, as occurred, for example, in 2014 in Saudi Arabia (EmTech MENA, 2019) and 2019 in Morocco (Gulf News, 2019), Yemen (Xinhua Net, 2019) and Iran (Motagh *et al.*, 2020). Other extreme weather events (storms, including dust storms, cyclones etc.) will become more frequent (Murakami, Vecchi and Underwood, 2017).¹² In Saudi Arabia the leadership has made the link between deforestation and increasing dust-storms in Saudi Arabia, explaining the co-benefits of the country's mass tree-planting initiative (Arab News, 2021). There is often a transboundary effect to dust storms: for example, South-west Iran is affected by dust blown in from Iraq (Javadian, Behrangi and Sorooshian, 2019).

Sea-levels will rise. By 2050, sea-levels may have risen between 0.2 (RCP 4.5) and 0.25 metres (RCP 8.5) at Tangier, Tunis, Alexandria and Muscat as shown in Figure 5 (The World Bank Group 2014, p. 129). Another example of high exposure is Oman . Under a 0.2 to 0.5 m rise, which is feasible in the 2030 – 2050 time period, 400 km² of total land area would be inundated, with “the Al-Batinah and Muscat governorates [being]... the most vulnerable under all SLR scenarios” (The World Bank Group, 2014; Al-Awadhi *et al.*, 2016). However, in terms of the number of people relative to total population at risk from sea-level rise, the UAE, Qatar, and Bahrain face the highest impact (Hereher, 2020).

¹² “While there are no direct projection studies on dust storms in the region, wind as a driving factor can be projected from climate models. However, there are no regional studies on changing wind patterns under climate change in the region as yet, and future trends have to be derived from global studies.” (The World Bank Group, 2014).

Figure 5: Sea-Level projections for Tangier, Tunis, Alexandria and Muscat
 Source: (The World Bank Group, 2014)

Storm surges will make the phenomenon even more destructive than the figures for the overall rise in sea-level would suggest. The fact that coastal areas are home to the majority of people in many MENA states makes sea-level rise a serious threat to residents and infrastructure. For example, Qatar’s INDC (Intended Nationally Determined Contributions) states that 96% of people in the country live in coastal areas (Ministry of Environment, 2015). According to one academic study, “Digital elevation models showed that there are more than 3100 km² of coastal areas that occur at 1 m level along the Arabian countries of the Gulf” (Hereher, 2020).

3.2 What could happen beyond 2050?

Looking out towards the end of the century, average temperatures will rise and heat waves will intensify in number, duration and magnitude under all scenarios (although the parameters used in the projections differ considerably) (Driouech *et al.*, 2020). By the end of the century, according to the World Bank, “highly unusual” heat extremes will occur in 30% of summer months almost everywhere in the region, even if global warming is held to 2°C.

If global warming reaches 4°C, there will be “unprecedented heat extremes” in 80% of summer months, by 2100. In a 4°C world [RCP 8.5], “warming continues almost linearly beyond 2040, reaching about 7.5°C above the 1951–1980 baseline by 2100” (The World Bank Group 2014, p. 121). Other sources project lower figures but use later (and warmer) baseline periods (e.g., RICCAR gives 3.2–4.8°C for the Arab world “towards end-century”, using 1986–2005 as the baseline (ESCWA et al., 2017, p. 89)). Under this

scenario, there may be more than 200 heatwave days each year by the end of the century for RCP 8.5 (Lelieveld *et al.*, 2014). The maximum temperature on the hottest days of the year would reach nearly 50 °C by the end of century for scenario RCP 8.5.

“Using a high-resolution regional climate model, Lelieveld *et al.* (2014) projected a substantial increase in the warm-spell duration [“heatwave”] index (WSDI) for several capital cities in the region (Table 4.2) [for 2071-99]. The mean WSDI over the observational period lies between zero and about one week; it is projected to exceed four months for most capital cities in the region in a 4°C world and even six months for Beirut and Riyadh” (The World Bank Group 2014, p. 124). In terms of extreme temperatures, the RCP 8.5 scenario suggests especially harsh living conditions by the end of the century, notably along the Mediterranean coast of eastern Libya and Egypt (ESCWA *et al.* 2017, p. 92). Iran’s cities will experience extreme temperatures, too (The World Bank Group, 2014, p. 123).

Most parts of the region will be drier than in 2050. “By the end of the century, both scenarios [RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5] suggest a reduction of the average monthly precipitation reaching 8–10 mm in the coastal areas of the Arab Domain, mainly around the Atlas Mountains in the west and upper Euphrates and Tigris rivers in the east” (ESCWA *et al.*, 2017). For the Jordan basin, one academic article projects a decrease in rainfall of 30% in 2070-2100 (compared to the baseline period of 1981-2010), while “multiple drought-type occurrences increase from ~8 in 30 years to ~25 in 30 years” (Rajsekhar and Gorelick, 2017). The same article projects a 28% decline in soil moisture and a 58% decline in streamflow (run-off) over the same period in the basin (assuming RCP 8.5), leading to an increased need for irrigation.

However, under the RCP8.5 scenario, studies generally project a substantial intensification of extreme precipitation events over the 21st century across the southern tip of the Arabian Peninsula (Yemen and to a lesser extent Oman) (Kharin *et al.*, 2013; Sillmann *et al.*, 2013). This is consistent with the robust projection for increasing annual precipitation over the Horn of Africa.” (The World Bank Group, 2014, p. 125) One academic study suggests an increase in rainfall in Yemen by 11% in the periods 2020-30 and 2040-50 (cf 2000-09) (Droogers *et al.*, 2012).

In most of the region, drought will increase, particularly under the RCP 8.5 scenario, with the Mediterranean and the western and northern parts of the Arabian Peninsula most strongly affected. The number of consecutive dry days (CDD) will increase, resulting in a lengthening of the dry summer season (ESCWA *et al.* 2017, p. 94). For Iran, the projections are less robust but predominantly show drought conditions that are less extreme relative to the rest of the Middle East and North Africa (The World Bank Group, 2014, p. 125).

Storms, including dust storms and cyclones will presumably be even more frequent and more severe than in 2050. A contraction of the area cultivated in the MENA region will expose soils to wind erosion, making dust storms more severe. There is no regional modelling on these phenomena as yet (The World Bank Group, 2014, p. 116).

According to the World Bank, sea level will not have risen at a uniform rate across the region by 2100. For example, Tunis will have risen less than Muscat, whichever RCP level is chosen, with Tangier (on the Atlantic coast) somewhere in between. “[P]rojected high-end rates of sea-level rise range from 6.4 mm per year (Alexandria) to 7.8 mm per

year (Tangier) in a 1.5°C world and from 20 mm per year (Tunis) to 21.4 mm per year (Alexandria) in a 4°C world (Table 4.5).” (The World Bank Group, 2014, p. 129)

One academic study asserts that “Iraq, KSA, UAE, and Qatar have the largest low-lying [sic] areas along the coast. The sea level rise by 1 m should overwhelm about 1910, 614, 270, and 147 km² of those countries, respectively.” The same study adds that “the UAE, Qatar, and Bahrain have the highest impact of sea level rise in terms of the number of population at risk to the total number of population ” (Hereher, 2020) A think-tank report notes that a two-metre rise by 2100 would flood a large part of central Doha (Lambert and D’Alessandro 2019). While this is considered unlikely based on current trends, feedback loops which could increase warming mean that this “cannot be ruled out” (Oppenheimer *et al.*, 2019).

3.3. Transboundary effects

Water supplies from outside the region (transboundary rivers)

There is considerable agreement among climate models regarding the future flow of the Euphrates and Tigris rivers, which rise mainly in the eastern Anatolian mountains of Turkey and flow through Syria and Iraq, and to Iraq respectively. “[A] runoff decrease of 25 percent to 55 percent [by 2100] is projected with 4°C warming [= RCP 8.5].” Snow-melt will occur earlier in the year, possibly affecting the potential for cropping (The World Bank Group 2014, p. 116). The position of downstream countries, Syria and Iraq will not only be affected by these trends, but also actions in Turkey, for example to retain more water for its own irrigation in reservoirs. .

In the Nile basin on the other hand, climate models do not agree to the same extent, as different parts of the basin may be affected differently by climate change. It remains unclear whether the Nile may carry more water entering Egypt in the future or less. Overall (?), the modelling shows a reduction in precipitation over the Blue Nile basin in Ethiopia, from which 60% of the water in the main stem of the Nile derives. Another 14% is contributed by the Atbara, which also rises in northwest Ethiopia. Projections show a decline in precipitation in this region of 3-6% by mid-century; they also show higher temperatures, which would result in increased evapo-transpiration and evaporation, including from the reservoir impounded by the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD). However, attempts to translate changes in climate into changes in run-off in the Blue Nile basin remain inconclusive, showing a wide range of different possible scenarios (ESCWA *et al.*, 2017, p. 125).

It seems clear, however, that the operation of the GERD will have as much impact on Egypt’s water supply as will climate change (Wheeler *et al.*, 2020). Once the reservoir behind the GERD has been filled (admittedly not a trivial matter or something that will be achieved quickly), Egypt will be in a better position than Syria and Iraq are: the dam’s purpose to generate electricity requires Ethiopia to maintain the flow.

Food security

A number of sources highlight the risks that climate change poses to global food supplies. “Climate change is projected to undermine food security ... Global temperature increases of ~4°C or more above late 20th century levels, combined with increasing food demand, would pose large risks to food security globally ” (Pachauri, Mayer and Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2015). More apocalyptically:

“a stoppage or reversal in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) ... would wreak havoc on food production globally ...”(Lenton et al, 2019). “In Russia, climate change may lead to a food production shortfall, defined as an event in which the annual potential production of the most important crops falls 50% or more below its normal average.” (Field et al., 2014)

The MENA region is heavily dependent on food imports, notably wheat, with over half the calories consumed coming from outside its borders (MENA-Forum, 2019). The main sources of wheat are the EU (specifically Poland, Romania and France), Russia, Ukraine, the US, Canada.¹³ In these circumstances, MENA countries are vulnerable to developments in supplier countries, which may, in extreme cases, restrict exports to maintain domestic supplies, as Russia (a major source of wheat for Iran and Egypt) did in 2010 (Welton, 2011) and 2014, following droughts. In 2010, the supply of Russian wheat to Egypt was cut by 500,000 tonnes, the equivalent of 5% of its total wheat imports (Devitt and El Dahan, 2014).

¹³ The EU accounted for about 36% of wheat imports to the region (Chatham House Resource Trade database 2020).

4. Vulnerability factors

While actual climate effects and events will be harsher in some parts of the MENA than others, the impacts on society and human systems will depend on many variables which will be in flux over the next few decades. The possible risk cascades and effects in the region (which are discussed in more detail in the next chapter) are conditional on a number of contextual factors that influence the vulnerability or resilience of affected people, economies, and political systems (see Box 4).

The likelihood of these risks materializing will depend on the evolution of these conditioning factors, which may look very different in 30 years' time. As such, **this section first describes the factors that will make an area more or less vulnerable to climate change impacts.** As we are particularly interested in understanding compound risks and the way that several pressures could result in transboundary and systemic impacts, **we also give weight to regional and international factors that could increase or reduce vulnerability.** The factors chosen – which combine 'sensitivity' and 'adaptive capacity' as described in Box 4 - have been identified from interviews with regional experts and our review of the literature.

Box 4: Defining vulnerability

Vulnerability to impacts can be measured in various ways because it depends on both the exposure to the hazard and the way the exposure can impact on people: the vulnerability. While the probability of a climate occurrence or trend might be the same in several areas, the impact on inhabitants may be felt differently depending on a number of variable factors. The RICCAR's Arab Climate Change Assessment Report (ESCWA et al., 2017) adopts a model building on the approach developed for the IPCC's Fourth Assessment Report (AR4) for assessing levels of vulnerability. This takes into account four variables:

- **Exposure** (changes in climate parameters that might affect socio-ecological systems either directly or through, for example, disrupting the flow of goods, finance, information or people into an area).
- **Sensitivity** (the state of the physical and natural environment that makes the affected systems particularly susceptible to climate change including population density, migrant and refugee populations and urban extent).
- **Potential impact** (determined by combining the exposure and sensitivity to climate change on a system).
- **Adaptive capacity** (the ability of a system to adjust to climate change categorized as: knowledge and awareness; institutional capacities, infrastructure, economic (including food imports) and technological resources and equity).

The *vulnerability assessment* takes into account 'potential impact' which results from levels of exposure and sensitivity factors and 'adaptive capacity'. Therefore, if the potential impact is high but adaptive capacity is high then vulnerability could be low to medium, whereas a lower potential impact could result in higher vulnerability if adaptive capacity was low.

Sensitivity to climate risk (and other trends and shocks) are not evenly distributed across the MENA region. Countries that depend largely on rainfed agriculture will be more sensitive to drought in terms of productivity. Some phenomena will be strongly felt where there is high density urban development in exposed geographic areas, for example, coastal Egypt, Gaza, Morocco and the Gulf coast.

However, the ability of MENA governments to cope with the additional challenge posed by climate change (**adaptive capacity**) also varies from one country to another. Access to finance, technology deployment and efficacy and preparedness of local and national institutions will make a difference in terms of the humanitarian outcome, economic losses and the period of disruption. For example, in spite of being in the path of tropical storms, Oman currently exhibits less vulnerability to climate change than Gaza, given the latter’s dilapidated infrastructure, much lower economic resources and land constraints.

Economic wealth is a key division in the region in terms of the ability to adapt to climate change. Fig X shows one proxy for this - GDP per capita - whereby the largest oil exporters and Israel stand out in contrast to the rest (The World Bank Group, 2014). These countries are able to access the technology and deploy large scale infrastructure (such as desalination, solar power and cooling) to mediate climate impacts as well as being able to import food.

Figure 6: MENA 2019/2020 GDP per capita (constant 2017 international \$)

Note: Lebanon, Oman and the UAE are for 2019, the rest are for 2020. Libya, Syria and Yemen data were not available. Source: (World Bank, no date).

However, an evaluation based on spending power and technology alone would miss two important points about adaptive capacity. Firstly, **sensitivities around consumption and living standards**. For example, while farmers in the Nile Delta and Jordan Valley might be poorer, with less technology, they also require less to maintain current standards of living and have traditional knowledge and experience of adapting to change. In the GCC countries and Israel, there are high expectations about standards

of living and citizenship benefits and less capacity to suddenly lower levels of service or resources. Falls in standards of living due to climate change therefore may more quickly entail a political backlash.

Secondly, **efficacy of government, civil society and private sector**. In this respect, Israel is better equipped to cope with climate changes than some of the richer Gulf countries because of its organisational ability and its exceptionally inventive private sector. Its status as a climate resilient country is, however, complicated by the fact that its government occupies Palestinian lands which are much less able to cope given occupation restrictions (see Box 11). This will inevitably draw resources into militarization rather than sustainability and increase risks to shared resources such as water contamination.

In addition, when looking out over the 30-year time horizon of this report, there are many local and international conditions which will evolve and change including demography, trade and forms of governance, that will all affect abilities to cope and adapt. The following outlines six non-climate factors under which fall several variables that emerged strongly in the literature and expert consultations, which will interact with climate impacts themselves, and are likely to influence vulnerability to climate change and its socioeconomic and political knock-on effects. These are **summarized in Table 2**.

Table 2: Summary of regional vulnerability/resilience factors and variables

Factor	Variables
Political stability	<p>Regional: Level of conflict, constructive/unconstructive level of cooperation or conflict in regional politics, state of conflict in countries, infrastructure damage</p> <p>Sub-regional: differences in sub-regional levels of peaceful cooperation/coexistence/tension, e.g. transboundary river relations</p> <p>International: interest and engagement from major powers</p>
Governance: Political will and efficacy of institutions	<p>Regional: Political will, rule of law/human rights, institutional efficacy including governmental competence, public perceptions of legitimacy and trust in state institutions, level of corruption and enablement, land management, water management</p> <p>Sub-regional: differences in sub-regional efficacy and governance coordination, e.g. sustainable shared water management plans</p> <p>International: aid, assistance and capacity building</p>
Governance: Local empowerment	<p>Level of decentralization of power (e.g. to municipalities); funding, quality of education and critical thinking, public awareness of climate change and environment; civil society competence</p> <p>International: Engagement and capacity-building at the local level</p>
Economic structure and well-being	<p>Regional: Economic health including income equality, ecological well-being, dependence on agriculture, dependence on high-carbon commodities, balance of trade, aid flows.</p>

	International: food prices; oil and gas prices; terms of trade; aid
Access to finance and technology	<p>Regional: Readiness for and access to credit and funds (including climate finance), technology transfer and innovation, energy, water and food pricing/subsidies, room for the private sector</p> <p>International: Availability of international finance including climate finance; FDI, engagement on technology transfer</p>
Demography	Regional: Population increase; age structure; mass displacement including rural to urban migration and cross-border migration

4.1 Political stability

The level of regional and national stability was flagged by most experts interviewed as a key determinant of attention to climate change issues and political will to address resilience and adaptation. Put simply, the immediacy of civil or cross border conflict – even if this does not erupt into military conflict - will mean that the attention of governments is diverted from planning for longer-term challenges such as climate change. Investments in adaptive projects and practices will be deferred. In addition, instability deters the necessary investment and finance (which was identified as another major vulnerability factor). Continuing instability in the region may mean that the attention of governments is diverted from planning to deal with longer-term challenges such as climate change. Moreover, instability or poor relations among states in the region may continue to hamper transboundary cooperation between states in confronting climate change.

Conflict damage also increases physical vulnerabilities (e.g. to water scarcity and temperature rise) and decreases basic resilience to societal impacts – e.g. through health centres, municipal administration and services (see Box X). The barriers to trade and actions of warring parties tend to create ‘conflict economies’ in which prices are inflated and safety and environmental regulations ignored. One current example of this is the destruction of oil refining facilities in north-eastern Syria and subsequent practice of ‘artisanal refining’ which is polluting soil and water, further reducing the options for future food and rural livelihood security as land and water come under pressure from climate change (Zwijnenberg, 2017).

Major power engagement

The interests and actions of major powers continue to play a heavy role in the region which can both support or harm peaceful relations. The US, the EU and various European states, Turkey, Russia and China are each engaged in development activities, trade including arms sales, diplomacy, military and humanitarian operations in the region. In general, the vying of different powers for control of certain regions has not proven conducive to peace in the region (e.g. Russia, Turkey and US in Syria), and neither has the overwhelming backing for one side (e.g. Israel-Palestine) or intervention to remove a dictator (e.g. in Iraq). The involvement of major powers in diplomatic initiatives has at times caused tension (for example the Trump administration’s attempts to broker a deal around the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (Chothia, 2020). However, more concerted diplomacy is essential to reduce conflict and to address shared environmental issues. The region is dependent on trade, investment, loans, aid and security interest from the international community. Changes in the level

of international attention – e.g. to security rents that maintain Jordan and Israel, will also change the balance of power in the region.

Occupation and militarization

The restrictions imposed when space is controlled by armed actors can have far-reaching consequences for ability to cope with climate change. It can inhibit adaptive migration as well as food-growing and selling strategies for example, worsening humanitarian conditions. The militarization of space is evident at national borders, but also in many internal parts of the region, particularly Syria, Iraq, the OPTs, Yemen and Libya. For example, combined with restrictions on freedoms (e.g. to get farm goods to market, to build water storage or have a say in water distribution plans that affect their access), the conditions of Israeli occupation in the West Bank inhibit Palestinian citizens' capacity to cope or adapt. Militarization of land, military checkpoints and confiscation all inhibit sustainable land management (as explained in Box 11). Mason and Mimi (2014) report that "*climate stresses are perceived by farmers to be less important than (post) occupational conditions in determining water availability. Israeli state practices are seen as harmful to farming livelihoods, e.g. prohibition and demolition of water infrastructure, land confiscation and/or restrictions, exclusive incentives to Israeli settlers, barriers to markets*" (Mason and Mimi, 2014). This is particularly true of 'Area C', the area of the West Bank under full Israeli control. In Gaza, the restrictions on imports of goods presents a severe barrier to adaptation.

War damage and reconstruction

Urban areas and essential infrastructure across Syria, Iraq, Yemen, Libya and Gaza have suffered large-scale damage and destruction due to multiple, recent and on-going conflicts. These countries also face severe levels of water stress and environmental degradation overlaid by climate change. Inadequate housing coupled with extreme temperatures and lack of access to power are already exacerbating inequalities across the region. In the coming years and decades, resilience to climate change and events will depend largely on the efficacy of reconstruction and regeneration of infrastructure and urban areas. However, the danger is that reconstruction is pursued in an ad hoc manner without consideration of future safety and local needs, locking in consumptive practices (namely energy and water demand) and unsustainable land use. This will increase vulnerability to climate changes. Reconstruction is already taking place and is likely to do so largely in a vacuum of environmental regulation, reducing countries' long-term prospects for the inclusion of returnees, social stability and economic recovery.

Box 5: Damage vulnerability

Damage to energy, water and food production and delivery infrastructure in conflict-affected countries exacerbates a critical situation for health and the economy in the coming years (ICRC, 2015). Urban devastation has been recorded in areas of aerial bombardment and/or ground level fighting in Iraq, Yemen, Libya and Gaza in over the last decade. Each country is suffering an acute shelter crisis, deteriorating municipal and public services including waste and sanitation, and dangerous levels of water and energy insecurity.

This damage amplifies societies' vulnerability with respect to climate change, increasing exposure to temperature extremes, water scarcity, disease and food

insecurity. Infrastructure to enable clean water and sanitation including water treatment plants, pumping stations, water towers, sewage treatment plants, often become targets in the fighting. In Yemen and Syria, conflict has dramatically reduced clean water access and proper forms of waste disposal in urban and rural areas and led to various outbreaks of hepatitis A, typhoid, leishmaniasis, and cholera (al-Zarier *et al.*, 2017, Zwijnenberg *et al.*, 2021). Israel's 2021 attacks on Gaza compounded food security in the country with direct destruction or damage to crops, animal sheds, greenhouses, citrus orchards and storage facilities as well as damage to irrigation channels and pumping equipment (The World Bank Group, 2021). Gaza already suffers from toxic metal pollution in soil caused by previous bombing attacks (Al-Najar *et al.*, 2015).

As Telhami and Zeitoun (2015) have shown with reference to several Middle Eastern countries, patched up infrastructure rather than more resilient recovery options after conflict damage can lead to more humanitarian suffering in time.

Displacement

Internal displacement and refugee flows resulting from armed conflict and insecurity have caused sudden and unexpected increases in population in some provinces and countries. In Syria, Iraq, Yemen and Libya, conflict has brought about the internal displacement of people to areas poorly equipped to provide for them. In Lebanon, Jordan and the Kurdistan Region of Iraq host large numbers of refugees which, even with immense international assistance efforts, has put pressure on services and housing.

4.2 Governance: Effective and inclusive institutions

In surveys carried out during the expert workshop, governance - including and political will to address climate change, institutional effectiveness, human rights and space for civil society - were the factors that most people identified as a key challenge for vulnerability to climate impacts and as the priority for resilience and adaptation.

Climate strategies

There is great variation in how climate change features in policy and planning across the region. Climate resilience and adaptation strategies are at an early stage. In Tunisia, climate change is part of the country's new constitution (Knaepen, 2021) while Oman and the UAE perhaps have the most advanced national climate change strategies (Luomi, 2020). All Arab countries except Iran and Iraq, Libya and Yemen have NDCs. However, this is not necessarily an indication of having an effective climate strategy in place. Palestine has a National Adaptation Plan (Smithers *et al.*, 2016) but lacks the capacity to implement it.

In general, MENA governments exhibit low levels of political will or capacity to plan for, rather than react to, natural disasters (ESCWA, 2017). Climate risks are generally not seen as something for which urgent preparations need to be made. Oman is an exception, having dedicated significant effort to disaster planning after Cyclone Gonu in 2007. Since 2010, Omani authorities have worked with UNESCO to develop a multi-

hazard early warning system (launched in 2015) and weather radar has been developed for cyclone and flooding warnings, allowing for evacuation of high-risk regions.

Institutional effectiveness

There are striking differences in terms of governmental competence – a crucial factor in determining resilience in the face of climate change. At the lower end are national governments that have little capacity to run their countries effectively (or even to provide security across the entirety of the national territory), even on a day-to-day basis (Yemen, Libya, Syria and Iraq are examples), let alone plan ahead. Recent evidence shows governmental competence declining rapidly in a state of conflict (as with the above countries) or as a result of stasis between political rivals and a power vacuum as it has in Lebanon. Some middle to higher income countries, including Jordan, Tunisia and Oman have relatively effective centralized bureaucracies but weak local-level governance. Weak enablement at the local level (e.g provincial and municipal governments) was an issue frequently cited by regional experts as a vulnerability across the region.

Some technical ministries (water, agriculture etc) have experienced well-qualified professionals but there is often a lack of joined-up government, with ministries of environment allocated little power in MENA political systems. MENA countries that have experienced conflict in recent years (Iraq, Syria, Libya and Yemen) have lost experienced professionals who have emigrated in search of a more secure life. These factors make it more difficult for MENA governments to protect their water and agricultural sectors from the impact of climate change. Notable successes have been achieved through long-term investment in skills and empowerment in key agencies. The role of independent electricity and water regulators in the GCC in fostering price reform and efficiency, the cooperation of the Saudi Energy Efficiency Centre and Zakat, Tax and Customs Authority in introducing efficiency standards, and the process of coordination between domestic and international bodies that has gone into DRR planning and preparedness in Oman are good examples.

In North Africa, some democratic reforms have taken place in Tunisia and Morocco, but reform processes have been either stagnant or reversed in more recent years. Despite efforts for decentralisation and empowerment of local and municipal authorities, government structures remain heavily centralised, with frequent protests erupting over the management and allocation of natural resources, notably water (Desmidt, 2021). This stands in contrast however, with considerable investments in renewable energy, notably solar power and green hydrogen in Morocco, making the country a frontrunner in Africa, with the country exporting knowledge and experts to other regions. While these plans have been lauded, it has also raised questions about the focus on export of green energy, rather than domestic consumption, and the technical and financial feasibility of these plans.

Land management

Poor land and water management practices add to the challenges of maintaining agricultural sectors in the context of climate change. The failure to correct these practices is often the result of governmental neglect of the agricultural sector in favour of sectors that produce higher economic returns and earn more foreign exchange. As

Waha *et al.*, 2017 note, “Land management practices are often inefficient and many policies favour urban populations and the supply of cheap food instead of supporting rural development ...”. This trend, more than drought, is likely to have prompted the urban-to-rural migration in Syria prior to the 2011 conflict (Khashan, 2016).

Another major problem for adapting to climate change is land control and land acquisition. Elite land grabbing, corruption and lack of by-law enforcement are self-rein. Corrupt practices and weaknesses in regulation are common features of MENA countries (The World Bank Group, 2014, p. 120). Both factors seriously undermine a country’s capacity to deal with climate change (and other challenges, for that matter). Corruption may lead to some rational measures being blocked by vested interests in or with connections to government; corrupt politicians and officials may siphon off international funding. At the large-scale project end, this risks inadequate and poorly maintained infrastructure (for example the non-functioning water treatment plants in Southern Iraq), while at the local level, it could mean that building regulations are simply not met, increasing health and flooding risks as was the case in Jeddah in 2009.

Water management

How water is managed is acknowledged across the region as the priority for adaptation. However, current conditions, water facilities and management are far from ideal and in many places, deteriorating, increasing the levels of vulnerability to water shortages and contamination. According to RICCAR, “The Arab region has long been subject to deteriorating water infrastructure due to deferred maintenance and the inability to dedicate financial resources for new investments (ESCWA *et al.*, 2017).” A critical issue inhibiting the necessary investment has been lack of regulation and/or pricing of water, in many cases enabling large businesses or favoured groups monopolize sources with little incentive for efficiency. In other cases, there may have been substantial investment in prestige projects with questionable utility for the citizens of the country concerned. Egypt’s large commercial agricultural developments are a striking example where colonial-era agricultural structures set up to exploit cash crops have consumed large volumes of water and technological resourcing, whilst delivering increasingly diminishing returns to people and the state (Mitchell, 2002, Masr, 2020).

Control of the sources of river water is to a large extent out of the hands of Middle Eastern countries. Egypt is the most extreme example, with over 95% of its water budget coming from countries upstream on the Nile. But Egypt is not alone: Syria, Iraq, Israel, Jordan are also in a similar position, being vulnerable to developments in upstream countries with which they share water resources. For example, Jordan will suffer reduced flows in the River Yarmouk when Syrian agriculture recovers to pre-conflict levels. One study estimates that the effect of that development would be twice as great as reduced precipitation as a result of climate change (Rajsekhar and Gorelick, 2017).

Lack of coordinated basin-wide management plans (there are none in the region to date) will lead to poorer outcomes in terms of MENA countries’ security of water supplies than might otherwise be the case. Such outcomes have already been observed in respect of the Euphrates-Tigris and Nile basins (Mueller *et. al.* 2021). The waters of the Euphrates and Tigris rivers, on which the food growing regions of Syria and Iraq depend, have depleted and degraded over the last 50 years due to a combination of

hydroelectric infrastructure, diversion for urban use, flood irrigation and chemical practices in agriculture (Shamout and Lahn, 2015). Although there is little evidence that overall water levels in the Nile Basin have reduced in recent years, climate change is causing more variation in the Nile's flow which increases the risk of flooding and extended droughts (Wheeler, K. et al, 2018)

Groundwater is still available to MENA countries but is rapidly depleting and poorly regulated. In most cases there is little effective effort to manage it as use is defined by land ownership and ability to afford and use pumps. In Yemen, for example, the water table is declining in places by as much as seven meters annually due to groundwater over-abstraction (Mohamed, 2017). In Gaza, the water supply is contaminated by sewage with 80 per cent exceeding the maximum salinity standard of the World Health Organization (Bromberg et al., 2018). In Algeria, the discovery and production of shale gas, seen as a way to respond to growing domestic demand and retain export markets, have raised serious environmental concerns over the destruction of fragile desert aquifers and water demands in southern parts of the country (Desmidt, 2021)

Given that 22 aquifers across the region (UN-ESCWA and BGR, 2013) are shared between one or more states, lack of cooperation presents a further obstacle to sustainable management. **An ESCWA study shows there are relatively few working shared aquifer agreements in the region.** Some have successfully begun the first steps in cooperation (see Box 6) which offer means to diffuse potential tension.

Box 6: Shared Aquifer agreements

Agreements on shared aquifers include the Joint Authority for the Study and Development of the Nubian Sandstone Aquifer System (NSAS) between Chad, Egypt, Libya, a steering committee amongst representatives from Algeria, Libya and Tunisia over the North-Western Sahara Aquifer System (NWSAS), and the agreement between Jordan and Saudi Arabia over the Al-Saq/Al-Disi aquifer.

For the time being, these remain largely communication mechanisms - the NSAS would come closest to full cooperation if it were operational (UN-ESCWA, 2018). A GEF-funded, UN implemented project has helped the Joint Authority to form a Strategic Action Plan, the long-term goal which is "to achieve an "equitable and reasonable" management of the aquifer, for socio-economic development and for the protection of biodiversity and of natural resources" (Quadri, 2017). This provides the groundwork for workable management once there is a stable government in Libya.

After years of low-level tension between Saudi Arabia and Jordan over the Al-Saq/Disi Aquifer (In 2014, Jordan began pumping water from it 350km to the capital city of Amman.), the two governments signed an agreement in 2015 and later set up a Joint Technical Committee. This set out regulations for limited drilling and defined a protected area.

With notable exceptions of the as yet unrealised Nile Basin Initiative and the NSAS SAP, existing transboundary water agreements tend to focus on shares rather than effective, sustainable cross border water-management. For example, while the Al-Saq/Disi agreement does have an emphasis on quality, it is based on shared use. The aquifer

became part of a ‘pumping race’ that had begun in the 1980s. The agreement provides high quality fossil water for municipal and limited irrigation use, but the source is non-renewable and some argue that this water should instead be treated as a ‘strategic reserve’ with recourse to other sources for irrigation.

For the most part, **transboundary cooperation over water can be understood in the context of broader security and economic relations between states** (Hussein, 2019). The Nile Basin Initiative for example has remained hamstrung by the reluctance of politicians to cede control to regional scientists and engineers who could create the joint understanding of the basin that is so desperately needed to generate cooperative action in the future. Progress on cooperation has tended to happen when leaderships recognize mutual security interests as they have done sporadically and bilaterally amongst countries sharing the Euphrates (Shamout and Lahn, 2015), even during periods of ‘imperfect peace’ (Mueller et. al. 2021)

4.3 Governance: Non-state and local empowerment

In interviews, regional experts repeatedly drew attention to three sub-state level factors that will be critical in addressing climate change effectively in future:

- i) the capability for decentralized decision-making and implementation by local authorities;
- ii) public awareness, capability and knowledge of climate and environmental issues and space for civil society organizations (CSOs) to operate effectively; and
- iii) private sector innovation and ability to deliver green and resilient solutions through the market.

Although conditions vary, these areas were considered as requiring improvement in the majority of MENA countries. Behind these issues lie deep and historical political-economy structures, and attendant weaknesses in rule of law, particularly in protecting human rights. Several experts also drew attention to cultural and educational legacies that have stymied creativity and critical thinking in the region.

Local governance

Local authorities are generally not empowered in the region, relying on centrally allocated budgets only, and with little devolution of power, for example over public buildings, infrastructure or basic services. Access to finance and resources to enable long-term municipal planning and investment for example, could enable much more effective and less expensive approaches for urban resilience. The work of the Greater Amman Municipality (GAM) in developing a climate action plan for Amman (Greater Amman Municipality, 2019), with support from international financiers is exemplary. As the GAM has an unusual level of independence and the capability to take on financial risk, it can engage directly with international partners and was also able to join knowledge sharing networks such as the 100 Resilient Cities and the C40 Cities. Another example is the past work of Ecopeace with mayors of towns sharing the Jordan River on reducing river pollution and treating sewerage (Djernaes et al, 2015). While not possible under current political conditions, such cooperation on shared natural resources suggests greater possibility for aligned crossborder remedial and adaptive action at the local level.

Civil society

Civil society is essential in preparedness and resilience. CSOs and community groupings can act in a way that is much more nimble and close to the ground than the government to educate, raise awareness, create networks of assistance and help with disaster response. Communities throughout the Middle East have mobilised on this basis to achieve improved outcomes in education, health and numerous other areas, despite prevailing conditions of poverty and marginalisation (Brixi, H. et al (2015). Following various disasters, including the Jeddah floods, citizens have self-organized assistance for affected people. In Egypt, the Hurghada Environmental Protection and Conservation Association (HEPCA), which focuses on conservation in the tourism-dependent Red Sea governorate, made notable progress in improving waste management policies and preserving coral reefs. It was able to do this through formal relationships with the local authorities “and has benefited from embedding itself as a localized effort supporting an economic lynchpin in the area” (Halawa, 2020). Likewise, predominantly business-focused associations such as country chapters of the Green Building Council and EDAMA - the sustainability business association in Jordan - have been able to push forward progressive regulation and standards regarding buildings and energy.

However, in authoritarian states in the MENA region, civil society organizations (CSOs) are often either heavily circumscribed by restrictions or essentially illegal, rather than being allowed to play an active role in organizing people, investigating potential abuses of power and making recommendations to the government. Environmental groups¹⁴, which were few in the region a decade ago, are a growing force in countries not plagued by conflict. While generally tolerated, these too can risk overstepping invisible and often moving lines which has happened in Egypt, Turkey and Iran in recent years. For example, the Iranian government has imprisoned environmental activists under charges of spying (Iran International, 2020). Those who speak out against environmental crimes are often also calling to attention high-level corruption or irresponsible decisions which may be considered a threat to regimes.

Civil society representation at the international level could help in gaining much-needed attention and support for the region’s climate and environmental issues yet this is currently lacking. It has, for example, been difficult to mobilize MENA CSOs (as well as those from several other regions) for the UN’s Environment Assembly (UNEA). To facilitate access, a proposal from UN Environment (UNEP) suggested altering the accreditation rule requiring two years of operations for an NGO/CSO. Many governments in the MENA region (and others globally) objected, instead requesting to specify 5 years of operations, stating the need to make sure organizations were genuinely active. “The real reason was to make sure they are not against the governments, even though these are environmental, not human rights organizations”, said one regional expert. In the end the existing rule was maintained but the episode illustrates the suspicion with which governments in the region view CSOs - unless backed by a royal family or government authority.

¹⁴ Given the difficulty of registering as an ‘NGO’, these are often either not formally registered as organizations or instead registered as welfare charities or social enterprises.

Private sector responses to sustainability

With the exception of Israel, the market in MENA countries remains dominated by the state and/or business elites with political connections. A state-led economy can bring a number of benefits with respect to climate resilience which might involve large-scale infrastructure, planned agriculture and national companies with technical expertise that can be deployed in a crisis. However, in practice, this model - coupled and encouraged by subsidized, untaxed inputs such as energy and water - has tended to crowd out entrepreneurship and encourage inefficiency. Lebanon exemplifies the way that politically connected cartels can inhibit reconstruction and basic services in a way that strongly impedes resilience (Boswall and Wood, 2020). A more level playing field, progressive environmental regulation and fairer competition and bankruptcy laws can encourage small and medium sized enterprises to offer the kind of creative responses to problems which are needed in the case of climate resilience and adaptation - as well as sustainable economic diversification for those countries threatened by future decline in oil demand.

Experiences of and potential for private sector actors in adaptive solutions vary across the region and must be understood within the context of the political economy of the country in question. In both Morocco, for example, the financial interest of elites has also created a strong incentive for renewable energy development and once regulation was in place, it opened up space for a growing number of local companies. This contrasts with Tunisia where the regulatory environment for renewables is weak although lots of technical support is being given (including from German development agency, GIZ), there are few incentives to expand the sector for the moment. The UAE has encouraged companies to compete on sustainability measures through increasing the introduction of standards and regulations for buildings' sustainability for example, and there are a few large conglomerates seeking to excel in this area. In Lebanon, a number of social enterprises and small businesses dealing with composting and recycling have sprung up in response to the state's failure to deal with a waste crisis in recent years (Aoun and Abou Moussa, 2019).

4.4 Economic structure and well-being

Poverty levels

Within each country, it will be the poorer sectors of society who will be least able to cope with climate impacts (Waha *et al.*, 2017). Among the problems facing them are the following: food prices may go up; poorer farming families may not be able to afford to drill deep wells to access ground-water; the areas in which they live may be more at risk of flooding than those in which the better-off live. There are already very low levels of investment in rural areas across the MENA and governments may not be as interested in helping them following extreme weather events, as they are in helping better-connected sectors of the population (World Bank, 2020b). Where governments are unable to help or are dilatory in doing so, poorer people will not have the resources to help themselves.

In wealthier MENA countries where energy is cheap and/or heavily subsidised, people will be able to use air-conditioning to cope with extreme temperatures. However, numerous groups including low-income households, migrant workers, IDPs and refugees may lack access to temperature-regulated housing or air-conditioning.

Importance of agriculture to the economy

The importance of agriculture to economies is another important determinant of vulnerability, particularly to drought and seasonal changes. According to the World Bank, agriculture, forests and fishing contribute 5.1 percent to the region’s GDP (excluding Syria and Libya), versus a global average of 4 percent in 2018 (World Bank, 2020a). However, if the agricultural value chain is accounted for, then this percentage more than doubles (Valdés and Foster 2010). (The World Bank Group, 2014, p. 117)” It is more important in terms of jobs and rural incomes as it employs an average of 10.7 percent of the total labour force (including Syria and Libya) while the share of total employment in agriculture ranges from under 1 percent in Israel to over 33 percent in Morocco (according to ILO modelled figures).

Figure 7: Agriculture’s importance to the economy

Note: no data available for GDP % in Syria and Libya. Source: World Bank World Development Indicators 2021.

Agriculture is also the sector with the highest rate of informality in the world. In the Arab world, 95.6 percent of agricultural employment falls within the informal sector (International Labour Office, 2018). Many of the workers relied upon in Jordan, Lebanon and the Gulf countries are expatriates, including refugees. Agricultural work is a vital contribution to refugee income in the region, and to family remittances in Egypt and Yemen (Tsukamoto, Leighton and Staermose, 2020). In the Middle East, a significant number of agricultural small holders and labourers are women (Abdelali-Martini and Dey de Pryck, 2015). Box 7 shows the vulnerability of these groups to climate change in the olive sector, given the current business model and gender conditions.

Box 7: Worsening inequalities in the profit-led Tunisian olive sector

Olive oil is Tunisia's key export commodity. Nearly a million Tunisians derive (part of) their income from olive growing. The olives sector is essentially in the hands of big

companies that, aided by the state, worked towards higher production levels via mechanization and intensive growth. The current business model does not provide good access to financial capital, including loans and credits to smallholder producers (Chebbi et al 2019) or encourage environmental replenishment.

Small farmers and women are particularly vulnerable. The mechanisation of large-scale capitalist farms has come at the cost of smallholders' dispossession and debt. While many small- and medium-sized olive farmers used to have various sources of income, most of them now only harvest olives. 90 percent of harvest workers are women, working as seasonal agricultural labourers. According to research by Gender Concerns International: "40 percent of women in rural areas are not well integrated into the economic and political life; they are illiterate and have no access to free healthcare. They earn a daily salary that is typically less than their male counterparts, who do the same work at the same time as suffering from social iniquity.

Mass production for export is draining the land, exhausting the soil of nutrients and reducing its fertility, and water availability. In recent years, a new type of Spanish olive tree varieties have been introduced in certain areas in Tunisia. While they produce more yields, they will require increasing amounts of irrigated groundwater that will put extreme pressure on already over pumped aquifers. Due to reduced water availability and increased droughts, yields from olive trees will further diminish in the near future.

The climate risks of the olives sector in Tunisia could further result in reduced production, especially in monoculture systems that are draining the soil. In the long run, reduced olive yields can cause supply losses and business disruptions for Europe. Moreover, social frustrations are rising due to inequality in the olives sector, where smallholders have limited opportunities (including due to the lack of access to credit and loans) in a sector that is in the hands of the large-scale agri-business. This could further trigger social unrest in rural Tunisia.

At the same time, there is fear that the DCFTA, if it would eventually be agreed, could further stimulate an export-oriented trade model, thereby undermining the flourishing of smallholder producers. Several factors that led to the 2011 'Freedom and Dignity Revolution' still prevail in Tunisian society. Without perspective, many young Tunisians are joining jihadi groups, which could form a direct threat to Europe. In addition, large groups of young Tunisians are migrating by boat to Europe, looking for better opportunities.

Source: adapted from Knaepen, H. (2021).

Balance of trade and food imports

With the exception of the recent blockage in Qatar, import dependence has not been a problem in the MENA region to date so long as three conditions are in place i) food producers are willing to export their products ii) there are means of transportation and supply routes available to transport the food and iii) a country has enough foreign exchange to pay for food imports (including in times of elevated prices). Countries with low volumes of water per capita and access to foreign 'rents' for example from oil exports, security arrangements and humanitarian aid have long pulled off this feat. However, there are several reasons that much greater economic diversification will be

needed to sustain growing imports in the future (Pouan and Hakimian, 2019). The effects of the Covid-19 pandemic coupled with sanctions in Iran from 2020, and the sharp inflationary impacts of the current economic crisis in Lebanon in 2021 illustrate the rapid effect that reductions in foreign exchange can have on food security.

Countries with larger export revenues per capita (namely the GCC, Israel, Morocco and Tunisia), or those with steady streams of other forms of international rent (Jordan, Morocco) are better equipped to make investments to prepare for climate impacts. The region's wealthier countries can afford to make investments that can help them cope with climate risks. Stockpiling food is one possible stratagem. Several countries keep high food stocks. For example, Qatar has developed its capacity to store food: its Strategic Food Security Facilities Project, a food storage and processing facility at Hamad Port, has the capacity to stockpile enough rice, sugar and edible oils for three million people (more than its current population) for two and a half years (Alagos, 2018) – although such strategies also often carry a heavy climate cost, as well as a financial one (Wellesley, 2019).

As fresh water sources dwindle, the Gulf countries have put restrictions on the growing of fodder for animals such as alfalfa, choosing instead to import growing volumes from North Africa and South America. Following the 2007 – 08 food price crisis, various state investment instruments and commercial agribusinesses in the GCC countries have invested in agricultural land in North Africa, Pakistan and the Americas. The jury is out on how effective these investments will prove to be, and may increase risks for other water-stressed countries (see the example in Box 7). More recent agricultural investments have tended to be in existing key trade partners in Europe and the Americas: for example, an Emirati company has invested heavily in Serbia and Saudi companies have invested in Poland, Ukraine and the US (Bailey and Willoughby, 2013; Cooke, 2016) while Qatar has invested massively in self-sufficiency (Wellesley, 2019).

Box 7 Unintended consequences of foreign land investments

MENA countries with substantial foreign reserves resulting from incomes from hydrocarbons exports, such as Saudi Arabia, the UAE and Qatar have, since the global food price spike of 2007/08, sought to improve their food security by investing in agriculture abroad. GCC countries made significant investments in land-rich but famine-prone African countries – particularly Sudan (Abdelaziz, Saeed Atallah and Eltahir, 2021)– although these investments have often faced poor security and political controversy (Lons, 2021). The UAE's investment in the Toshka project in Egypt is one such example (Jägerskog and Kim, 2016). This began in 1997 as an initiative to reclaim 540,000 feddans (2268km²) of the Western desert and shift the population from the Nile Valley. Despite ambitious targets, the Toshka project has not improved food security in Egypt. Neither has it brought many other benefits to the country, as the farms owned by foreign UAE investors require high amounts of energy while not delivering on the promise of generating many new jobs for Egyptian citizens. The two biggest Gulf companies invested in the project are now controlling almost half the 60,000 feddan (62280 acre) of cultivated land, drawing water for irrigation from Lake Nasser at remarkably low prices. Despite the government's promises of wheat production, the area is mostly being used for export products (dates and grapes) and highly water intensive animal feed cultivation like alfalfa (Masr, 2020).

Such “defensive strategies” are generally beyond the reach of low- and middle-income (LMI) countries with much lower capacity to prepare for and adapt to the direct and indirect effects of climate change, (Borghesi & Ticci, 2019).

Looking to 2050, simulations suggest that dependence on agricultural imports is likely to continue to increase in the MENA region, especially in the event of stronger climate change (Tull, 2020). Current forms of agriculture and dietary patterns as well as little scope for expanding land use in the region further support this trend. (Razzaz *et al.*, 2017). Countries that do not have large quantities of forex at their disposal (especially those with large populations, such as Egypt) may struggle to feed their citizens if they are to meet other needs as well. Providing for twice the number of people without rationing or dietary substitution will mean using twice the amount of forex, even in years of plentiful supply on the global market. In years of supply-side shocks, such as poor harvests in grain-exporting countries, the forex bill will obviously rise. So will the cost of any food subsidies. If climate change brings widespread crop failure in supplier countries, it may even prove difficult to provide an adequate diet for ordinary people. MENA regimes may find themselves having to choose between spending a large chunk of their national budgets on subsidising food or risking popular discontent by not doing so.

However, across the region, different methods and types of food production, dietary change and a reduction in food waste could enable an increase in locally produced food (or at least stem its decline) whilst increasing nutritional intake and therefore robustness to disease (Bahn, EL Labban and Hwalla, 2019).

Dependence on revenues from high-carbon industries

The transition to a decarbonized energy system globally will entail a contraction in the markets for fossil fuels. While the timing of this is uncertain, the IEA’s 1.5 degree celsius scenario demonstrates the dramatic fall in coal, oil and gas demand needed to meet the goals of the Paris Agreement and avoid dangerous climate change. Even if the actual trajectory is more chaotic, the falling costs of alternative ways of meeting energy needs and declining economic capacities to purchase fossil fuels on the international market as a result of climate change impacts will constrain oil and gas markets.

This presents a challenge for countries of the MENA region whose economies are dependent on oil and gas exports, such as Algeria. Paris-aligned trajectories tend to consider prices over the next two decades within the \$70 - \$30/barrel range, while many of the MENA countries, given rigid government budgets including subsidy and civil services salary payments, rely on over \$80/barrel to break even. Algeria is estimated to even need \$ 135/barrel to break even (Desmidt 2021).

The chart below gives some idea of the vulnerability of countries to falls in hydrocarbons prices.

Figure 8: Economic dependence on hydrocarbons measured by share of GDP per capita (bubble size and label) and share of merchandise exports (%)

Note: GDP per capita is for last year available (2016 – 19) using World Bank Development Indicators

All those on the chart are exposed (Yemen and Syria perhaps more so but no data was available), but the larger bubbles give an indication of which countries are likely to have a larger wealth cushion in terms of sovereign wealth and other investment funds. The further to the right the country, the more it relies on hydrocarbons exports for the foreign exchange needed to pay for food imports and other foreign goods. The three countries at the far right, Algeria, Libya and Iraq, appear the most exposed of all to falls in oil price, with almost total dependence on hydrocarbons for foreign exchange and relatively low GDP per capita.

There are however, several other considerations; one is the capacity a country has to diversify its economy - which would include its human resources and skills potential, its land fertility, other natural resources, tourist attractions and national capacity for innovation. The less able a country is to diversify, the more vulnerable it's economy will be to shifts in demand trends. For countries such as Algeria, low oil prices, difficulties in attracting investment partners, infrastructure gaps, and technical problems have meant that the investments in renewable energies are lagging behind considerably. While not facing (potentially) high-level conflict such as Libya and Iraq, much-needed and anticipated political and economic reforms have stalled in recent years. This has hampered efforts to diversify Algeria's economy and energy markets, fuelling popular protests.

4.5 Access to finance and technology

Access to finance will be essential for resilience and adaptation in the lower- to middle-income countries in the MENA region. Each country will have different options given its particular context and relations with development finance and investors. Regional experts drew attention to the specific needs for finance specifically to enable introduction of efficient and circular technology in the water and agricultural sectors, as well for nature-based solutions and remediation of land and water

sources. For example, water production through desalination, increased deployment of solar power and hydroponics are examples of other capacities that higher income countries are well placed to implement. Weatherizing and protecting built infrastructure, as well as building back better in terms of much needed regeneration and reconstruction in conflict-affected areas. Much of the needed measures are not currently commercially profitable so will rely on a mix of public funds, national and international.

However, in order to both attract and optimize the benefits of climate finance (as with other types of finance that could support these kinds of resilience and adaptation investments), proposals will need to show the potential to scale which will mean addressing the options enabling national public and or private capital to flow in. However, as Egypt, Jordan and Morocco have shown through their success in scaling up renewables, it is often the regulatory environment rather than the money that is key to attracting finance and deploying technology. Developing project pipelines which show how initial finance will help to mobilize other forms of capital and lead to transformative results on the ground.

The challenges of access to climate finance in developing regions are well documented and some reports detail specific issues for the MENA region (ESCWA, 2019, UNFCCC, 2021, UNEP-FI, 2021). These strongly relate back to the governance issues noted in 4.1 and 4.2 but also the way international climate finance remains fixated on donor priorities, fragmented, and still lacking a firm footing for measuring adaptation gains. To date, Egypt and Morocco have been the recipients of the largest share of climate finance to the region in the form of grants plus finance from the Clean Technology Fund (CTF). Energy and transport have received the majority of climate finance to date (ESCWA, 2019). Projects have been largely under the category of 'mitigation' - chiefly for renewable energy - but with a small but increasing amount in the region is focusing on 'adaptation' and 'multiple foci' (Watson and Schalatek, 2021). For example, in 2020, Jordan and Lebanon attracted USD 14 million through the Adaptation Fund USD 14 million for managing a number of water-related urban challenges "to increase the resilience of displaced persons and host communities to climate-change-related water challenges in urban host settlements" (UNEP-FI, 2021).

As Fig 9 shows, several countries in urgent need of support for mitigation and adaptation have received relatively little, and some, namely Syria and Iran where private finance flows are heavily constrained by international sanctions, are missing from this picture (although they have recently accessed GCF funding through the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) to build their capacity for attracting and deploying climate finance (FAO, 2021).

Figure 9: Amount of climate finance approved for MENA recipient countries (2003–2020)
 Source: (Watson and Schalatek, 2021)

4.6 Demography

Quite apart from any impact of climate change, countries in the region will be confronted by challenging levels of population growth. The population of the region as a whole is projected to increase by around 43% by 2050 compared to 2020. There are, however, wide variations in rates of growth among individual countries, with the highest rates projected to be in Egypt, Iraq, Israel and the Occupied Palestinian Territories (United Nations, 2019). Egypt is the most populous country in the region and Iraq the third, so the absolute additional numbers will be high, too (United Nations, 2019). High fertility rates also mean a high percentage of young people, although overall in the region, fertility rates have been gradually declining as more women go through higher education, get jobs, and delay having families (Roudi-Fahimi and Kent, 2008). This trend may speed up, meaning lower-than-expected rates of growth. Nevertheless, growth is the trend which means greater pressure on national and municipal services including water, energy and waste. Given that climate change will make it more difficult to sustain agricultural output at existing levels, exacerbated by changes in diet, population growth becomes an additional driver in increasing dependence on imported foodstuffs.

Large-scale migration is likely to continue within national borders, across borders in the region and from outside the region. As of 2019, the region had an estimated 12.4 million IDPs and 9.1 million refugees, chiefly from conflicts in Syria, Iraq, Yemen and Libya as well as the historically unsettled matter of the Palestinian refugee population. The MENA region is also a transit route. As Desmidt (2021) points out, the sub-Saharan Africa to North Africa route is well established in spite of its many risks. With the effects of both climate change and conflict being felt most acutely in Sub-Saharan Africa, it is likely that migration will continue in this direction (Barnes-Dacey and Dworkin, 2020; Idemudia and Boehnke, 2020). It is also possible that new routes will emerge as political dynamics shift as described in section 5

Whether or not migration increases or decreases vulnerability depends on several factors, including the capacity for reception and integration in the receiving

community, level of pre-existing social ties, the legal rights of migrants, and the state of their living conditions. One probable result of the projected decline in the agricultural sector in MENA countries (see section 2) is migration from the countryside to urban areas (Wodon *et al.*, 2014). This was strongly emphasized by regional experts during the interviews and workshops. Observation of this sort of movement, already much in evidence over the last two decades in Egypt, Iraq and Syria, suggests that the majority of migrants from rural areas will establish themselves in the marginal areas of towns and cities which often lack adequate access to services (Waha *et al.*, 2017).

Unplanned migration has tended to add to environmental stresses on receiving areas, while displaced people living in temporary shelters and without community support networks are among the most vulnerable to climate and weather extremes (Lahn and Grafham, 2015). This is due to the way in which migrants are received and the pre-existing conditions in the receiving country. Informal settlements, as with IDP and refugee settlements, are often built in haste and lack infrastructure (or legal provision) for sewerage, waste, water treatment and energy. This is also the case with many aging, degrading urban 'camps' and cities housing internally displaced peoples and refugees in the region, namely the Palestinian ones in Gaza, Jordan and Southern Lebanon for example. Restrictive policies, lack of access to housing, jobs markets and services play a critical role in these conditions. Coping mechanisms in the event of not being able to keep warm or cook food for example may involve burning waste or cutting trees. This may in turn increase hostility towards new groups from local inhabitants. Such issues present growing humanitarian and equitable development concerns.

5. The likely effects of climate impacts on human societies and systems in the MENA

The intersection of climate impacts and the above-mentioned vulnerabilities, if unaddressed, will result in impacts on **human health, livelihoods and economic opportunities, inter-communal relations, and regional security**. In this section we discuss the prospects for these four elements based on available studies and use examples of five risk cascades (based on expert consultations and workshop dialogue) to show how **compound risks with cross-border effects** could play out.

The shape and severity of outcomes will depend on the context for response and resilience measures. This context, both regional and international, will evolve and change over the next few decades. Selected variables identified in table A1 in Appendix 1 as the most important in affecting the severity of climate impacts in the expert interviews, form the parameters for three simple, non-exhaustive scenarios: ‘Stagnation’, ‘Fragmentation’ and ‘Cooperation’. These were tested at an intensive workshop in March 2021 and improved upon. Each scenario (set out Appendix 1, summarized in Box 8) plots a different version of those parameters.

Given the pace of change in technology and difficulty of predicting this, and the increasingly strong influence that climate change will have on international and regional trends, **the scenarios are imagined as a broad characterization of trends from 2025 to 2035**. We can then imagine these evolving until 2050. It is also possible to imagine each scenario applying to a different sub-region at the same time or one scenario leading to another.

The purpose of the scenario and cascades exercise was twofold:

- to help think through the way that climate impacts might play out in the MENA under different conditions, and what the implications might be for Europe
- to understand priorities for resilience-building and adaptation and in particular, the way that international partners like the EU might support it.

As such, the five risk cascades consider what might happen in certain sub-regions under the ‘Stagnation’ scenario. A box under each one suggests how things might play out differently under the ‘Fragmentation’ and ‘Cooperation’ scenarios.

Box 8: Future scenarios

Scenario 1, ‘Stagnation’, is marked by increasing ethno-religious tensions in the region. States remain militarily strong with centralized bureaucracies. Authoritarian rule inhibits civil society and reduces inclusion, accountability and transparency. Economies remain undiversified and rent-based. In the absence of defined rights and laws, antagonistic relations stymie attempts at greater regional trade integration. Food import dependency increases. Economic and educational inequality grows. High population growth drives urbanization and crime; under-employment is common. Balances of trade worsen and debt rises. Climate change is addressed through technical fixes, reactive action and vanity projects in richer countries, in place of regional, long-term, inclusive strategic planning. Securitization tightens borders in wealthier countries, restricting inward migration.

The US withdraws from the region with the exception of trade and strategic aid. Russia and China strengthen influence. Global finance is limited although uncoordinated ad-hoc aid and security packages are available. Food prices in the region are higher with sporadic price shocks. Oil prices are volatile to lower.

Scenario 2, 'Fragmentation', is marked by greater fragmentation of states, the rise of new actors, and uncoordinated decentralization of power. Simmering regional tensions prevent greater integration of trade. Food import dependency remains high. Governance is uneven: some breakaway regions are supported to improve capacities while others become more feudal. Porous borders enable increased smuggling and human trafficking. The private sector expands in some areas but not in others. An imperfect peace exists between riparians. Population growth is unevenly distributed, driven by conflict and migration. Economic inequality grows while formal job growth is weak. Tensions and fragmentation inhibit effective, long-term implementation of climate adaptation strategies.

Major powers pursue tactical diplomacy in the region. Other powers provide increased strategic investment, responsive aid, and modest climate-resilience finance. Food prices are volatile with some price spikes. Oil prices are volatile to medium.

Scenario 3, 'Cooperation', is marked by a gradual decrease in conflict and greater attention to cooperative, diplomatic solutions in the region, enabling increased investment, finance and technology innovation and adoption. Institutions are strengthened and there is greater decentralization of authority to local governments. Rule of law, regulation and clear market incentives foster improved land and water management as well as a vibrant private sector, helping hydrocarbons-exporters to manage the transition. Food import dependency is sustainably reduced by increasing regional cooperation in trade and water management, coupled with nationally diversified food production. Population growth slows and there is greater planning for and acceptance of migration flows. Educational quality and equality improves. Jobs are increasingly generated by the private sector, while universal income assists the transition to automation. Balance of trade improves and debt falls.

The international community is strengthened by enhanced cooperation on development and security, and coordination of aid and (climate) finance. Food prices remain volatile to high with some shocks. Oil prices rise and then fall as alternative technologies and regulations take hold.

5.1 Human health

Environmental degradation, whether driven by climate change or other factors, can have a wide range of negative health consequences, both direct and indirect (Green *et al.*, 2013). Climate change effects may favour the spread of certain communicable diseases, including dengue, malaria, hantavirus and cholera (Wu *et al.*, 2016). Heat stress from more severe and longer-lasting heat waves may be the most serious threat to human health caused by climate change in the MENA region (Zittis *et al.*, 2021). **Humidity may become the most serious challenge, especially for coastal cities.** A wet-bulb temperature (TW) of 35°C, which is an air temperature of 46°C with humidity of 50% can kill a person as their body will not be able to cool itself through sweating. As fig 10 shows, the TW has come close to this in several locations in the

Arabian Gulf including Dhahran, Ras Al Khaimah and Muscat. Bolleter et al. (2021) explain how this will be worsened by sea level rise and the concentration of buildings in areas of the UAE coastline. Pal and Eltahir (2016) argue that this could severely affect life in the region, including the international pilgrimages (*Hajj*) to Mecca (Pal and Eltahir, 2016).

Figure 10: Historical and projected wet-bulb temperature extremes in the Arabian Gulf
 Source: Pal and Eltahir, 2015. “Averages for the domain excluding the buffer zone (DOM), land excluding the buffer zone (LND) and the Arabian Peninsula (AP) are indicated in each plot.”

Figure 11: Observed extreme humid heat in the Gulf region, maximum for 1979 - 2017
 Source: Adapted from Raymond et al. (2020).

Certain groups will be more vulnerable to the health impacts of climate change than others, as detailed by Waha *et al.* 2017. For the elderly, the WBT threshold may be lower, while both old and very young are more susceptible to heatstroke. One academic study estimates that the mortality risk to those over 65 will be three to seven times higher in 2100 (compared to 1951-2005), even if warming is kept to 2°C (Ahmadalipour, Moradkhani and Kumar, 2019). Other groups at risk will be “The rural poor, unskilled workers and internally displaced people – all large populations in the region ...” (Benzie, Davis and Hoff, 2012). Many refugees and displaced people live in temporary shelter and conditions even less adapted to extreme conditions. Even today it is not unusual for temperatures to reach into the mid-40s in camps like Azraq and Zaatari in Jordan (Albadra *et al.*, 2017). People who work outdoors or who cannot afford additional air-conditioning (e.g., the poor in urban heat-islands such as Cairo and migrant construction workers in the Gulf countries) will also suffer. Soldiers undergoing training or in combat may be affected, too (Stoltenberg, 2020).

According to an opinion piece in the British Medical Journal, “without effective interventions and cross-border cooperation the changing climate will continue to impact on increased level of morbidity and mortality resulted from infectious diseases in the region, with the most vulnerable groups in society at greatest risk” (Paz, Majeed and Christophides, 2020). High temperatures (especially when combined with flooding) may result in increased outbreaks of salmonellosis, cholera and giardiasis (Wu *et al.*, 2016). Floods also increase the opportunities for standing water in which malaria-carrying mosquitoes can breed and create conditions for diseases such as West Nile virus, Ebola, and Zika (El-Zein *et al.*, 2014). A rare outbreak of West Nile fever occurred for example during a heatwave in Israel in 2006 and 2010 (Paz, 2015; Efron, 2021) or in Iran in 2008 and 2009 (Sayed-Ahmed, 2016)..

Increased concentrations of pollutants in water supplies including salts will occur as a result of a decline in flow in rivers and streams and reduced rates of aquifer recharge. This effect can already be observed in the Euphrates and in the Gaza Strip for example. If treatment to remove these pollutants is not of a sufficiently high standard, diseases will become more prevalent. This may happen directly (when people drink the water, as has occurred with mass hospitalizations in Yemen and Iraq¹⁵ or indirectly (when people consume food crops irrigated with polluted water or fish from polluted rivers).

Air pollution resulting from dust storms (potentially combining with other forms of pollution such as that from traffic and heavy industry) brings other forms of health hazard, including respiratory diseases (El-Zein *et al.*, 2014; Soleimani *et al.*, 2020; Khanjani, no date). **Storm-damage to critical infrastructure (hospitals, transport networks etc.) can have secondary health impacts, for example, if patients are unable to get medical treatment or medicines.** Secondary health impacts may also result from food poverty consequent on the non-availability of food at affordable prices.

5.2 Livelihoods and economic opportunities

According to the FAO, climate change and increasing water demands mean that “the region is expected to experience economic losses estimated at 6 -14% of GDP by 2050” (FAO, 2020).

Agriculture

In most MENA countries, agriculture is the sector likely to be affected most severely by climate change. The reduced availability of water through reduced precipitation will be a major factor. So will higher temperatures, which will bring higher rates of evapo-transpiration, meaning less crop per drop (Farajalla, no date). For example, Tunisia is likely to experience a 14% increase in evapo-transpiration by the 2050s (Mirzabaev *et al.*, 2019). In addition, higher temperatures will reduce the productivity of agricultural workers (Jobbins and Henley, 2015) (as well as other people who have to work outdoors, such as construction workers).

Sea-level rise will reduce the area of cultivable land in MENA (through effects such as sea-water intrusion into coastal aquifers and flooding resulting from storm surges),

¹⁵ This can already be observed in Yemen, although the increased pollution is not associated with climate change (El-Zein *et al.*, 2014)

thus reducing agricultural production. The areas likely to be affected include some of the region's most productive farmland, e.g. the Nile Delta, the Atlantic coast of Morocco and the coastal plains of Oman (Shammas and Jacks, 2007; Al-Maktoumi et al. 2018). The compound effects of drought, poor domestic and transboundary water management and resulting soil salinization are shown in Fig X (Nile). Sea-water intrusion is accelerated by over-abstraction from coastal aquifers or declining river flows, mainly for irrigation or to supply cities (ESCWA et al., 2017). Effects on animal health and ecosystems will also increasingly affect rural livelihoods. Salinization resulting from reduced river flows and seawater intrusion has already led to animal deaths in Southern Iraq, driving farmers into greater poverty (Elia, 2018).

There is some disagreement as to how fully the question of the effects of climate change on agriculture has been studied (Field et al., 2014) as much depends on precipitation patterns, water management, crop varieties and farming techniques. Some sources boldly declare that longer droughts will mean a reduction in the area within which rainfed cropping is possible (as well as reduced rates of recharge of non-fossil aquifers used as a source of water for irrigation). For example, the World Bank 2014 report states that "By mid-century, 8,500 square kilometres of rainfed agricultural land will be lost (Verner, 2012)." "Reductions in crop productivity of 1.5–24 percent are expected for the western Maghreb and 4–30 percent in parts of the Mashreq, by mid-century (The World Bank Group, 2014)."

Box 9: Food insecurity and job losses in the Maghreb

Fig. 12 shows the potential ramifications of such conditions that might be felt across Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia under the **Stagnation** scenario. The risk cascades here are common to several other MENA countries but with notable impacts for the EU in terms of:

- A combination of higher temperatures and water shortages reduce volumes of export crops causing disruption in food supply chains
- Increased migration to the EU as opportunities for education and income generation decrease
- Pressure on diplomatic relations as heavy state repression of protests and/or instability spreading across borders

Under the Stagnation case, these outcomes are also fostered by:

- heavily centralized decision-making
- incoherent water management policies and strategies, lack of maintenance of water infrastructure and unsustainable use of water for industry (e.g. gas fracking in Algeria, phosphate industry expansion in Tunisia and Morocco) and export-oriented agriculture and energy (water use in cooling power plants and solar facilities).
- continued and rising reliance on subsidies
- gender inequalities
- lack of regional cooperation

How might this play out differently?

Fragmentation: Where power becomes much more fluid and decentralized, foreign-backed corporate agri-businesses assume greater power in certain places, challenging democracies. More porous borders and militia-led local economies foster black markets, making trade more difficult, and increasing people and drug trafficking to the EU. Socio-economic economic inequalities widen, with some groups benefitting from greater investments by agro-business while others are further excluded.

Cooperation: Increased regional trade - including with sub-Saharan Africa but also between countries in North Africa - strengthens the economic position of Maghreb countries; foreign assistance supporting a timeline for phase-down of oil and gas production and growth of RE and alternative revenue streams in Algeria helps to alleviate water and economic pressures. Greater decentralization offers opportunities to respond to local challenges in more responsive ways. Financing for and increased access to climate resistant crop varieties, weather insurance and regenerative and gender-inclusive farming coupled with improved EU market access revives rural communities and stems rural-to-urban migration.

**Fig. 12 Climate risk cascade:
 Maghreb food security**

Several academic studies have noted the likelihood of temperature extremes amplified by a reduction in soil moisture resulting from decreasing precipitation in the Middle East and Mediterranean (The World Bank Group, 2014).” In the region’s oases, reduced rainfall together with other drivers such as poor water-management practices may lead to increasing salinization. Moreover, higher temperatures may limit the range of crops that can be grown in oases (Mirzabaev *et al.*, 2019).

While quantification of the impact of climate change on agriculture in the region is challenging, **some trends seem certain to manifest themselves in the absence of radical change in food production methods:**

- MENA countries will have to spend more foreign exchange on importing food. For countries like Egypt that already depend heavily on food from abroad and have limited forex income, this will be an additional burden.
- The urban poor will be faced with increased food prices (Waha *et al.*, 2017), unless governments increase subsidies (which will add to budgetary pressures).
- MENA countries will become more vulnerable to any disruption of global food supplies, for example, as a result of crop failures in supplier countries.
- The contribution of agriculture to GDP in individual MENA countries will fall. For example, Iran’s INDC estimates that the national economy would lose \$3.7bn each year in damages from 2015 to 2030 compared to 2010 “due to the changing trends of climate change and hydrological parameters” (Department of Environment of the Islamic Republic of Iran, 2015). In some countries (especially those where the sector is negligible in terms of GDP, such as the Arab states of the Gulf), this effect will be barely noticeable; in others, such as Morocco, Tunisia and Egypt, it will be substantial.
- Employment in agriculture will fall. Although agriculture is often only a small part of MENA economies, it is in some countries a major (informal) employer.¹⁶ The social consequences of any decline in the sector will therefore be greater than the impact on the economy of individual countries. Many of those who cannot find jobs there will try to emigrate (Farajalla, no date).

Competition for water among different sectors (agriculture, industry and commerce, domestic etc.) will continue to grow as demonstrated in the Maghreb cascade. However, new approaches and innovation in farming practices can reduce this. Different sectors can be complementary to some extent. Irrigated agriculture can make use of treated wastewater from domestic and industrial uses (as can golf courses and other tourist facilities, such as hotel gardens). Treating and re-using wastewater does, however, require the construction of additional infrastructure and a high degree of organisational efficiency and regulation, to ensure the water has been treated to a safe standard. So far, Israel is the only country in the MENA region that has used wastewater for irrigation on a large scale (Water Scarcity Solutions, 2016). Other

¹⁶ According to the World Bank, agriculture employs 34% of Moroccan workers, with equivalent figures for Egypt, Iraq, Iran, Tunisia, Lebanon, Syria and Algeria of 23%, 18%, 18%, 13%, 13%, 10% and 10% respectively. For all other MENA countries, the figure is below 10%. (World Bank, 2021)

countries in the region have mostly not managed to overcome the obstacles involved which include proper regulation and safety precautions as well as farmer awareness (Fanack Water, 2017). This could change if what are at present pilot projects in the region are demonstrably successful. Public-private partnerships in this regard are slowly taking form, for example in Morocco, where some thirteen desalination plants are planned under the National Programme for Drinking Water Supply and Irrigation (2020-2027). These are mostly intended to secure drinking water supply, including in coastal, urban and tourism-dependent centres such as Agadir and Casablanca (El Kharraz, 2020).

Damage to urban businesses and assets

Flooding is an important phenomenon affecting the MENA region, especially since the region has little experience with floods and flood prevention, due to its predominantly arid or semi-arid climate (Loudyi and Kantoush, 2020). Longer dry periods followed by heavy rainfall can increase the risk of flooding given that dry soils will become more impermeable (Vaghefi *et al.* 2019). **Together with population rise and un-resilient urban expansion, the impacts of flooding are likely to intensify.** More frequent and/or more intense storms could also cause damage to infrastructure (electricity distribution, transportation etc.) (Farajalla, no date). Coastal wetlands of the MENA region will also be strongly affected by storm surges (Dasgupta *et al.*, 2009).

According to the World Bank, “a study of 136 coastal cities identified Alexandria, Benghazi, and Algiers as particularly vulnerable to a 0.2 m sea-level rise by 2050. The study projected that, in the event of the failure of flood defenses, the effects of sea-level rise would increase damages from \$16.5 billion to \$50.5 billion in Alexandria, from \$1.2 billion to \$2 billion in Benghazi, and from \$0.3 billion to \$0.4 billion in Algiers. Annual losses would increase to \$58 billion, \$2.7 billion and \$0.6 billion with 0.4 m of sea-level rise for these three cities respectively. A sea-level rise of one meter could impact 10 percent of Egypt’s population, five percent of its urban area, and decrease the country’s GDP by six percent. One study estimated that a sea-level rise of 0.30 m (projected for 2025 in this study) would flood 30 percent of metropolitan Alexandria, forcing about 545,000 people to abandon their homes and land, and leading to the loss of 70,500 jobs. With a sea-level rise of 0.5 m, projected for 2050, the same study calculated that about 1.5 million people would be displaced and about 195,500 jobs lost.” (The World Bank Group, 2014).

Alexandria is particularly at risk because the area is sinking. It is ranked top among the cities with projected increased loss of local GDP as a result of damages from sea-level rise by 2050 (The World Bank Group, 2014). Basra in Iraq is also highly vulnerable (Khamis, 2020).

Inadequate infrastructure is a major problem. **The lack of drainage in cities mean that flooding increases hazardous conditions for driving with roads quickly becoming submerged.** The collapsed buildings and bridges suggest that rapid development and poorly constructed infrastructure compounds the problem. This has already played out in parts of Amman, Jeddah and Muscat in the last few years. In each place, an adequate drainage system would have reduced the damage (Daoudi and Niang, 2019; Al-Naamani, 2016).

More frequent and/or more intense storms could cause damage to infrastructure (electricity distribution, transportation etc). This could have a devastating impact on the business and tourism economies in the GCC with global ramifications.

Box 10: Infrastructure loss and damage in the GCC

In this risk cascade, damage to coastal infrastructure in the GCC combines with system vulnerabilities such as reliance on desalinated water to create negative economic cycles and service crises which weaken the social contract. Figure 13 shows the GCC quite generically, but there would be specific risks for each country.

Risks that could transmit beyond borders include:

1. **Massive damage to coastal infrastructure** in freak weather events and large-scale flooding causing direct and indirect deaths; business losses and insurance payouts.
2. **Opportunities for diversification beyond oil and gas – notably tourism and fishing - are reduced** through climate events. This has impacts on international investments and assets in the region, particularly property.
3. **Internationally invested sovereign funds diverted for domestic reconstruction**, potentially impacting on international financial flows.
4. **Expatriate communities are adversely affected, causing diplomatic tension.**
5. **Mass movement of people** – for some countries the situation could become so dire that the government attempts to relocate the entire nation to another country – at least temporarily – with legal and political ramifications. For example, the country of Qatar with its small native population could in theory afford to buy a temporary home in a less populated part of Asia.

How might this play out differently?

Fragmentation: This would signal a momentous change in the GCC, where the fall or contraction of monarchies could give way initially to a chaotic grab for infrastructure and worsening states of disrepair, further endangering human life. Loss of control over major oil installations and nuclear power (UAE) could result in catastrophic outcomes but more likely, increased international intervention would give rise to corporate-led security and patch-up solutions. Ad hoc technological fixes such as cloud seeding and genetic modification may be unacceptable to religious groupings and become a point of conflict with corporations or governments.

Cooperation: Increased deployment of disaster risk reduction (DRR) measures, early warning systems and local infrastructure measures would strengthen resilience to storms. Empowerment of local municipal governments and civil society would enhance pro-active mitigation and response strategies. Increased enforcement of regulations and by-laws, and improved urban design would help protect people and businesses from the worst effects of heat, storms and flooding. GCC countries' technical expertise and innovation would enable growing business in renewable energy trade, carbon management, and sustainable solutions, helping to diversify as oil revenues decrease.

Figure 13: Climate risk cascade: GCC

The impact of sea-level rise on cities and infrastructure

The combination of sea-level rise and storm surges could do a great deal of damage in countries such as Egypt, Morocco and the GCC states (e.g., Oman, where around 400 km² of land area could be inundated by sea-level rise alone, assuming a rise of 0.2-0.5 metres - a possibility within 20 years) (Al-Awadhi *et al.*, 2016). **This trend threatens coastal areas in many MENA countries, where a great deal of infrastructure (ports, factories, cities etc), the most productive farmland and large numbers of people are located** (Figure 6 in the ESCWA Water Development Report here: shows the percentage of people living within 100kms of the coastline.) (ESCWA, 2017). Those MENA countries that are economically resilient may be able to afford the cost of relocation of infrastructure and people from affected areas; poorer countries may not. While sea level rise is a slow onset impact not generally thought to have significant impact in the MENA region until the latter part of this century, the deltas of important rivers may be the exception. In locations such as the Nile Delta, sea level rise could exacerbate existing problems of subsidence, salt intrusion and poor drainage, with local consequences for housing, employment, and food production by 2030 (Jobbins and Henley, 2015).”

5.3 Social relations, communities and rural-to-urban migration

If the impact of climate change on agriculture is severe (as seems quite probable, particularly under an RCP 8.5 scenario), **many rural communities may well disappear or radically change their demography**. Those most likely to leave first will be the young and enterprising, particularly (initially) men; this will change the demographics – as has happened in many Sahel villages, with women gaining greater agency but also overburdened by familial and agricultural responsibilities. Cities to which rural people move may find it difficult to cope with the new arrivals who, like the existing population, need additional jobs, infrastructure and services (housing, education, health etc.).

Migration of this kind can cause clashes between established residents and newcomers, if the informal and formal mediation and legal structures are not able to deal with such problems. Such tension could result, for example, if the newcomers put an additional strain on services, they may be discriminated against based on ethnicity (Waha *et al.*, 2017) and conflict with local communities may arise due to differences in cultural norms and practices. There is already an extensive literature on the consequences of rural-urban migration but far less that relates this phenomenon specifically to climate change. The article by Waha *et al.* (2017) is a notable exception.

Unrest could result if a government favours one social group or geographical area over others. This could be the case, for instance, if the authorities draw on groundwater in rural areas to supply cities, in a situation in which reduced rainfall has curtailed the resource. A similar phenomenon has already been seen in Yemen, although not as a result of climate change (Small Arms Survey, 2010). Service failure in the context of inequalities has already proven a trigger for unrest. Violent protests erupted in Basra in 2018 following over 100,000 people being hospitalized as result of drinking local water supplies. This demonstrates how **a failure of basic services can be a trigger for outrage over a host of popular frustrations**. In Basra, these frustrations arose over the growing wealth gap, unemployment and corruption; all thrown into sharper relief in the context of Basra’s status as an ‘oil rich’ province where

there are also wealthy enclaves not exposed to the polluted water. The pollution itself is likely to have been a result of a number of factors including upstream damming and poor transboundary river cooperation, poor national water management, climatic variability, corruption and governance failures that meant that existing treatment plants were not working (Lahn and Shamout, 2018, Rubaie et al 2021).

Climate change could also trigger pathways to internal tension or conflict between social groups that do not directly or at least initially involve the authorities. **Reduced precipitation as a result of climate change may exacerbate existing inequalities and tensions in farming communities.** Water tables may sink because of reduced recharge, with the consequence that only better-off farmers who can afford the equipment and the diesel for pumps will have access to groundwater. This has already happened in Yemen, although factors other than climate change are responsible (Lackner, 2019). **Situations are likely to occur in which one group can use its superior wealth, power or political connections to gain unequal access to a dwindling resource.**

In the Palestinian territories, constrained and unequal access to water is a point of tension between Palestinian and Israeli settler communities but also increasingly amongst Palestinian households.¹⁷ Inter-tribal armed conflict in Southern Iraq provides a precedent of what can happen when there is not adequate recourse to methods of resolution as communities vie for shrinking resources.

In areas already affected by conflict and/or political injustice, climate factors could worsen the status quo. However, **in many places, political injustices and the daily experience of oppression are the overriding concerns.** These tend to inhibit the implementation of resilience measures, leaving communities and economies more vulnerable to climate impacts. EU and European development banks are investing heavily in climate resilience strategies and various water-energy-food related infrastructure in the Jordan Valley area. For example, the European Investment Bank set up a framework loan of 260 million Euro to support investments in Jordan's water sector in 2020 (Elnimr, 2020). The overall annual investment of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) was 87 million in 2019 and 73 million in 2020, 73% of which were invested in sustainable infrastructure (EBRD, no date). Yet their success depends on political factors. Box 11 illustrates how climate change could play into a developmental decline in Jordan and increasing instability in the West Bank in the context of these non-climate dynamics.

Box 11: West Bank de-development and inter-communal tensions

The area of the Jordan Valley is politically contested and highly securitised. In places, it runs through the state border between Israel and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and contains part of Palestine, known as the West Bank.

The West Bank area of the Jordan Valley is fragmented in terms of authority. Following the Oslo Agreement, the area became subject to complex political categorizations which determine usage and access. According to the human rights organization B'Tselem, almost 60% of the West Bank is under full Israeli control, known as Area C under the Oslo Agreement. The remaining 40% — home to Palestinian communities,

¹⁷ CASCADDES MENA Interviews, March 2021.

including the city of Jericho — are divided between Area A (full civil and security control by the Palestinian Authority) and Area B (Palestinian civil control and joint Israeli-Palestinian security control) (B'Tselem, 2017). 46% of the Jordan Valley in the West Bank has been declared military firing zones, although this overlaps with the state lands allocated to Israeli settlements. Israel has also declared one fifth of the area as nature reserves with the vast majority of it overlapping with the two categories above (B'Tselem 2017; Etkes and Mishirqi-Assad, 2013).

Israel's militarization of the Jordan Valley region, various forms of land and water control and settlement building have already forced many farmers to give up their rural livelihoods and to seek other sources of income in cities or even as wage labour in settlements (Mason and Mimi, 2014). This pattern of rural to urban migration weakens community cohesion and usually leads to increased urban poverty and inequality.

Looking forward, increased water stress and reduced agricultural productivity are likely to push already marginalised groups of Palestinians living in the Jordan Valley to breaking point. Continued expansionist policies in which Israel encourages, subsidises and protects illegal settlements which consume significantly more water resources — and enjoy a higher standard of living than their Palestinian neighbours — would only exacerbate the unequal resource distribution and the latter's sense of injustice. Migration to urban areas and wage labour into Israeli settlements will effectively depopulate rural areas, further reducing the potential for a future Palestinian state since abandoned land is more easily appropriated.

Increased water stress and reduced food security could also raise the stakes of returning or retaining the West Bank land and water resources to Palestinians. While there is no fair means of representative engagement in water governance or resource to just resolution for resource conflict, violent attacks between Palestinian communities and settler communities over areas using water resources (such as olive groves and orchards) may intensify.

Ultimately, continued oppression by Israeli military and authorities coupled with rural-to-urban migration by Palestinian farmers and extreme economic inequality can create the conditions for a new economic Intifada. This would in turn affect Israeli farmers, increase rising food prices, could increase the sense of crisis in Israel and result in increased polarisation and possible domestic unrest, further weakening Israel's ability to govern.

Jordan meanwhile, governs the eastern bank. This forms an important part of the Jordanian economy, both in terms of agricultural products for export and the domestic market, and for tourism. But water insecurity mars the prospects for rural livelihoods and development in the area. Given the precarious nature of the Jordanian economy and potential for increased securitization of development policies, rural areas could become neglected or suffer double blows from failing crops, uncoordinated export and agricultural policies, and increased competition for water. Meanwhile, increasing military oppression from the Israeli side is likely to worsen relations with neighbouring states including Jordan, whose leadership will come under greater public pressure to withdraw from cooperative and diplomatic agreements with Israel.

Fig 14 demonstrates the extent to which socio-political factors exacerbate and compound natural resource stresses and climate change in the region and how in

future these could undermine the effectiveness of international – including EU – investments in climate resilience in both areas and further damage the prospects for peaceful development.

How might this play out differently?

Fragmentation: Humanitarian crisis in Gaza and West Bank affects Israeli communities in the form of water pollution and disease; civil disobedience and popular unrest follow. Hit by more waves of migration without sufficient aid, Jordan's ability to function as a state decreases with reducing ability to service debt. Some opportunities arise for joint civil society action on land regeneration as military control of the West Bank recedes. International agencies increase their humanitarian role in the region [need help on this one]

Cooperation: Greater international and regional pressure and engagement forces resumption of peace talks. Occupation ends and recognition of shared environmental resources and a commitment to environmental justice as the basis for a new pathway to peace between Israel and Palestine – either as a one or two state solution. Innovation and technological capacity grows through sharing knowledge and cross-investment. Equitable management of the Jordan River Basin and replication of best available sustainable agricultural techniques enables increased food production, while agricultural planning makes sure that the region can produce the right quantities for export and domestic sales.

Source: Jordan Valley case study, Lahn and Elgendy, forthcoming 2021.

Fig 14: Climate risk cascade: Jordan Valley

5.4 Insecurity, conflict and cross-border migration

Political responses to the effects of climate change are extremely difficult to predict but will be the key variable in any risk scenario. Regimes in the region may be very different in 2050 or 2100 from their current character: for example, further rounds of uprisings in Iran and the Arab states may bring transformations that previous rounds failed to do. There could be greater fluidity and fragmentation or new territorial boundaries with different ideological leanings and alliances. Some of the broad possibilities are discussed in the scenarios (see Appendix 1).

The impacts of climate change will not be the sole cause of unrest. It is possible however to see pathways to political instability in which climate change plays some part. Such pathways are laid out in another paper in this series on security in North Africa (Desmidt, 2021) and examined more closely in Section 7).

The severity of climate change as a factor in instability depends on the extent to which there is already distrust and frustration with governments and on whether they are seen to prepare and respond effectively to climate change impacts. They also depend on how the authorities respond to any dissent related to or triggered by climate impacts, with repression possibly more likely to lead to instability (at least in the long run) than softer measures such as dialogue (Ghabra, 2018). **An extreme weather event that is badly handled by the authorities for example might combine with factors such as unemployment, high food prices and the absence of freedom of expression to cause street protests.** Such an event could also bring into existence a grass-roots movement filling the needs gap and altering power dynamics in the country, much as the Muslim Brotherhood did in Egypt earlier this century.

On the other hand, **governments themselves may choose to ‘securitize’ climate change**, that is, to treat it as an existential threat above normal politics which requires extraordinary measures. This could enable counter and adaptation measures to be fast-streamed. **It could also be used to justify policies such as the hard closure of borders, restrictions on mobility, land seizures, and alliances with neighbouring countries to secure preferential access to goods.** This is not difficult to imagine given the high level of centralization in most MENA governments and the recent experience of COVID-19.

Extremist groups

For their part, extremist groups have not engaged explicitly with climate change to gain support and recruit members. However, there is some anecdotal evidence of such groups taking advantage of the impacts of climate stresses. In Iraq, for example, drought and lack of water for irrigation which has driven thousands to migrate from rural areas and has also led to tribal conflict in Iraq (Al Hasan, 2020), can also be seen as critical factor in increasing the vulnerability of men from farming communities to ISIS recruitment (Schwartzstein, 2017). In future, government inability to deal with climate events could become a touchpoint for insurgency, especially if there is a strong popular reaction to extreme weather events that extremist groups could exploit.

The likelihood that contracting employment opportunities in agriculture will cause migration from rural areas to the cities to accelerate has already been mentioned. In countries affected by sea-level rise, there may also be migration from coastal cities

such as Alexandria or Basra to other cities. If the region's economies and governments prove able to generate jobs, infrastructure and services to cater for these new arrivals, the process need not be especially disruptive. In many cities at present, however, planning, administration and implementation capacity is lacking. In those circumstances, those who find themselves without jobs and services could be prone to take their discontent to the streets or be attractive targets for recruitment by extremist groups.

Conflict between states

The effect of reduced flows in shared rivers as a driver of international conflict involving MENA states may be slightly less challenging to isolate. However, whether conflict does or does not occur in such situations depends more strongly on the overall relationships between states than it does on the availability of the resource.

In terms of MENA states' relations with other riparian states, climate change may be an exacerbating factor or the trigger for the escalation of an existing dispute. Globally, internationally shared rivers have served as much to promote cooperation between states as they have to promote conflict (Wolf, Yoffe and Giordano, 2003) (as shown below in Box 12). This has not been the case so far in the MENA region and the future might possibly even bring more cooperative relations, perhaps including comprehensive treaties among all states that share a river basin.

Box 12: the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) and cascading climate risks

The Nile is the longest river in the world and the lifeblood of the 550 million inhabitants (Lashitew and Gebeyehu, 2020) of its 11 riparian countries. Of those, 75% live in rural areas, where their livelihoods depend on the cycles of nature and the availability of water resources (Tront and Jagerskog, 2020). The Nile Delta accounts for 30-40% of Egypt's agricultural production [can we get numbers for the other countries?] (ESCWA et al., 2017). Egypt, Ethiopia and Sudan are already dealing with significant food insecurity and nutrition challenges and populations are set to increase significantly in the coming decades.

At the heart of increasing tensions in the Nile Basin is the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) – set to become Africa's biggest hydroelectric dam when complete. Egypt and Sudan, who lie downstream, fear that Ethiopia, as the dam builders, will effectively gain control of the flow of the Nile, a turn of events that radically changes the way that water resources have been shared in the region. For its part Egypt has declared the project a major threat, against which "all options are open". As the diplomatic dispute endures however, Ethiopia has carried on with the construction of the dam, and has begun filling its reservoir in July 2020, aiming to have the 74 BCM project fully operational by 2023.

Any change in water quality would have a huge impact on the vast majority of Egyptian and Sudanese farm holdings that are considered as 'small' – the majority of which are on the banks of the Nile. And changes in water volumes might increase desertification and loss of livelihoods, potentially causing civil unrest if not addressed properly. The environmental impact of the GERD on the complex Nile River system also raises concerns about the river's ecosystem, the surrounding environment, and the river's downstream course.

Fig. 15 shows a potential scenario in which the construction of the dam without adequate cooperation exacerbates existing trends already negatively impacting soil salinity and the ability of smallholder farmers to make a living through rain-fed agriculture. These impacts in turn worsen the effects of drought and food insecurity, increasing rural-to-urban migration and domestic unrest while national governments also earn less revenue from agricultural exports. In this 'stagnation' scenario – governments throughout the region react by doubling down on agricultural 'mega-projects' as a means of generating revenue for the state and deflect attention from domestic governance failures by upping the rhetoric and actions against riparian states, thereby undermining the options for cooperative water agreements and pushing external partners – such as the EU – into defensive strategies around migration management.

How might this play out differently?

Fragmentation

Nile Basin states continue along a trajectory of tense rivalry and fiercely nationalistic development planning. This focus neglects existing water infrastructure, leading to increasing risks of damage or breach. At the same time, individual states aggressively pursue the development of alternative water sources, for example the Western Nubian Sandstone aquifer and replicate the same structural problems of water consumption and use already in existence throughout the region. The role of the EU in disaster response and humanitarian assistance increases.

Cooperation

Increasing pressure, and resource-backed commitments to diplomatic and technical cooperation initiatives such as the NBI – finally lead the riparian states to undertake a coordinated project of regionally focused water management which maximises environmental and social benefits of the water available. Long term cooperation agreements create, over time, a new generation of environmentally minded technical experts (and politicians) who recognise the importance of regional water management for the future economic prosperity of the region. At the same time, early warning systems implemented across the region, proactive strategies for climate conscious land management systems, and large scale investments in national adaptive capacity help to avert the worst of the impacts from future climate impacts.

Source: Nile case study - Dahshan and Owen, forthcoming 2021

Fig 15: Climate risk cascade: Nile

Securitized state responses

Box 13 gives the example of how compound agricultural and urban climate-related stresses could exacerbate insecurity and migration from Iraq.

Box 13: Iraq

The risk cascade illustrated in Figure 16 shows how several dynamics could combine with climate change impacts both within and outside the region exacerbating violence, loss of life and health, and food insecurity. This could result in outward migration, reduced oil exports and inability to service debt. These risks have to some extent already played out in the region, although environmental factors have often been ignored or marginalized given the impacts of invasion and ‘regime change’ in 2003, ongoing political and militarized conflict, and ethno-religious dynamics. Electricity is also a potential source of increased cross-border tension. Dust storms in Iraq have already caused electricity outages in Iran, affecting oil production in Khuzestan Province and provoking accusations against Iraqi authorities (Alarabiya News, 2017).

Under the **Stagnation** scenario described in fig. X, sub-optimal reconstruction efforts with little or no consideration for climate change or sustainability and ongoing elite land capture would further weaken trust in government. Reductions in services such as sudden electricity outages would result in protests and increasingly repressive state counter measures. A further ‘securitized’ measure might be that Iraq comes more fully under the hegemony of Iran in a protectorate model with increasing backing from China and Russia for finance, security and debt.

Climate-related factors that could affect this are:

- **Increased rural-urban migration** without sufficient investment in municipal services and deteriorating living conditions in Iran and Iraq.
- **Reducing international oil prices** as the global energy system decarbonizes. As a country where oil receipts fund around 90% of government revenue, and requires a rising oil price (over \$70/barrel in 2021) to meet budget requirements, Iraq faces severe economic consequences if unable to diversify its economy fast enough.
- **Sporadic reduced production of oil**, affected by water and electricity declines.
- **Declining domestic agriculture combined with international food price rises**, presenting a serious current account imbalance.
- **Increasing dust storms affecting neighbouring countries, increasing securitized responses.** For example, climate stresses combined with sanctions on Iran could also increase opportunities to securitize events such as electricity outages.

Fig 16: Climate risk cascade: Iraq

How might this play out differently?

Fragmentation: As state control is increasingly ceded to militias backed by different external forces, assets such as oil and electricity infrastructure fall into different hands. Resource stresses would force groups into undertaking more ad hoc decentralized solutions; artisanal refining would become rampant in some places, further worsening local pollution; but cooperative solutions over water use and solar power might also be able to take root out of necessity. This scenario is likely to promote increased migration and trafficking routes from South and Central Asia through Iran and Iraq. A number of 'narco states' could arise as a result of lack of law and order and receding alternative income-generating opportunities.

Cooperation: Mutual recognition of shared climate and environmental challenges fosters closer relations over water and ecology as the international community makes more nature-based financing available. Greater decentralization of power would encourage a race to the top in terms of local municipal resource efficiency and service provision with circular measures increasing urban agriculture. Greater equality and quality in education and rule of law would enable a multiplicity of businesses and social enterprises to thrive, decreasing dependence on oil revenue as that declined. Regional trade (including food for electricity trade linked to cooperative water management between Turkey and Iraq) would also improve. However, a recalibration of the balance of trade would still be needed and international food price spikes would present a challenge which some level of regional storage-sharing might help meet.

6. Recommendations: What should MENA governments do to meet climate-related challenges and how can governments and international organisations outside the region assist them?

In the MENA region, **adapting to climate change is not a government priority** and comes below many other concerns linked to security and economic stability. State failure in these areas will also damage the prospects for implementing resilience. It is therefore important that climate resilience and adaptation projects are **designed to include immediate co-benefits that meet country needs** and align with national aspirations. Given the transboundary nature of many of the risks we discuss above, it is also possible to consider **how measures might promote greater cooperation**, for example through knowledge sharing and technical exchanges, infrastructure that benefits more than one country, cross-border community land restoration and joint early warning systems and DRR cooperation.

Capacity to plan and implement varies widely across the region, and amongst our expert respondents, **governance was the most oft-cited impediment to greater resilience** – or cited as the first thing that needed to be addressed. Mismanagement and corruption, constraints on civil society, the entrenchment of vested interests, insecure land tenure and lack of access to justice present major obstacles to effectiveness and are often responsible for making things worse on the ground (Cofman Wittes, 2016). It is therefore important to make sure that resilience also strengthens governance and accountability, while acknowledging imperfection of working conditions, especially in conflict-affected areas with complex ‘conflict economies’ (Eaton et. al. 2019).

Insecurity was also high on the list of impediments to resilience and worsening sensitivity to climate impacts. For some MENA countries (Yemen, Libya, Syria and to a lesser extent, Iraq) continuing internal conflict means that many measures that could be taken in more stable circumstances cannot be taken for the time being. For Palestine, Israeli occupation has a similar effect. In terms of investment, it would be a waste of resources to build a state-of-the-art waste-water treatment unit, if it is bombed a few months later. Likewise, imperatives for providing shelter for people in conflict zones and those fleeing or returning from conflict will override the best laid plans for smart, net zero-carbon cities. These situations currently severely inhibit the steps that need to be taken now, in terms of adapting to present and future changes in the climate.

There is however a growing body of experience on the relief to resilience approach whereby **meeting immediate humanitarian needs can also contribute to longer-term development and resilience objectives** (BMZ, 2021)¹⁸. There have been some successful projects for example deploying community-level solar solutions through women-led businesses in Yemen (UNDP) and innovative shelter-improving projects in Jordan. The international ‘build back better’ agenda is also embracing the concept of **‘sustainable reconstruction’ in post-conflict zones** to try to make sure that communities coming out of war are not left more vulnerable to resource stress and

¹⁸ The EU, its member states and its partners have therefore launched the Resilience and Humanitarian-Development-Peace Nexus, introduced at the 2017 Council Conclusions (European Commission 2021b).

climate change. The Arab region has only recently received attention on this front (UNHabitat, webpage). Whether **environmental cooperation and projects can be instrumental in restoring or maintaining peaceful relations** between parties is an area worth continuing to explore. To be successful, it is likely that **it will need to be backed by serious external brokerage and diplomacy and strong awareness of complementary interests.**

The literature on adaptation reflects the wide range of policies that governments, sub-national authorities and individuals could adopt in order to adapt to climate change. The IPCC's Summary for Policymakers for example suggests a range of measures across physical, institutional and social areas, many of which will need to be pursued simultaneously (Pachauri et al. 2015). For the foreseeable future, however, **most MENA leaders are likely to prefer the "structural/physical" responses**, particularly those in the "Engineering and built-environment" category, in the IPCC report. Such responses are less complicated politically (vested interests are not threatened and may well be able to benefit) and may attract donor funding, soft loans etc.

Access to finance for adaptation is currently hampered on the domestic side by the lack of coordinated strategic planning for climate change, capacity to draw up viable projects and a market and regulatory structure with impediments to scale up. However, it is also inhibited by fragmented international conditions for climate finance, donor-led priorities in mitigation and the lack of metrics to assess and price adaptation progress.

In terms of reducing overall economic vulnerability in the context of rising food prices and the global energy transition, countries will need to address their balance of trade and economic diversification. **The process of economic diversification must be a political priority.** This process cannot be effected at speed, a country will usually need a timeline of decades to reduce its dependence on hydrocarbons rents for example. Economic progress for exporters should be measured not so much in terms of GDP growth (which is heavily influenced by the price of oil and gas), but in terms of diversification into activities which are not dependent on the sector or on government spending reliant on the revenues from the sector.

6.1 General recommendations

More use could be made of the various UN funding facilities aimed at assisting countries to adapt to climate change. One think-tank report argues that Arab governments have under-utilized these facilities (Lambert and D'Alessandro 2019). The work of the League of Arab States and UNESCWA encourages country governments to take advantage of opportunities for climate finance and a range of green technologies. The new UNESCWA Arab Centre for Climate Change Policies may be able to go further in connecting the dots.¹⁹

The UNDP carried out an assessment of adaptation projects in the MENA (including countries further south that we do not include in this assessment) and identified a number of lessons learned including the importance of working on enabling policy and governance environments, promoting participative project design, decentralizing management and facilitating community involvement; making sure projects can be

¹⁹ <https://archive.unescwa.org/arab-centre-climate-change-policies>

operated and maintained sustainably and putting in place cost-recovery and finance recycling mechanisms (Twining-Ward et al. 2018).

These lessons raise **the importance of taking the local context into account**. According to the IPCC, it is "... essential for the approaches to be based on an understanding of local community structures." (Field et al. 2014). Where this has not happened (in the field of development generally, not just in respect of climate change), the results have been disappointing or even the opposite of those intended (Lackner 2020). As the history of urban reconstruction in Lebanon and Iraq shows, certain large infrastructure or real estate projects, while favoured by national governments, may divert resources away from the most urgent community needs, generating discontent (Sirri, 2021; Boswall and Wood, 2020).

In the same vein, **it is essential that more materials and scientific evidence is produced in or translated into Arabic**. One expert said "availability of data in the region is so hard and gets harder when you go looking for reporting in Arabic." This can prevent the progress of legal actions and therefore accountability in cases of environmental transgressions.

EU engagement: Reducing the risks of initial impacts

The initial impacts defined by this project focus on three areas: food insecurity, loss and damage as a result of storms and impaired landscapes (coastal and agricultural) unable to support populations. In terms of needed resilience measures, improved **water management** is a theme that runs through each of these, followed by **regeneration of landscapes** and **built infrastructure resilience**. These are far from comprehensive but provide a priority list.

Experts were keen for the climate challenges facing the MENA region to be understood as integrated with those of Europe, given the issue of migration to the North. "Europe will be on the receiving end of what happens in the region in terms of food, resources, supplies", said one participant. CASCADeS MENA Expert workshop participants generally felt that the EU was doing a good job in the region. The EU's work and projects were well-known amongst experts in Jordan and Palestine, North African participants were more aware of the Union of the Mediterranean partnership. In these places, people felt that the EU carried diplomatic leverage as a major player and could therefore encourage governments to give higher priority to climate change and adaptation while also supporting an enabling environment. There appeared to be room to make sure that the EU's planning was joined up and coordinated with other UN initiatives in the region.

Water management

The countries of the MENA region are frequently characterized as 'water-scarce' which is why desalination has been a popular solution against the availability of much less natural water per capita. This characterization can, however, detract from opportunities for far greater efficiency and resourcefulness than desalination, especially given its impacts on sensitive coastal regions and emissions if powered by fossil fuels.

The number one requirement for demand-side management is to price water efficiently. The pricing of water is politically sensitive, as sudden rises in tariffs in

Saudi Arabia in 2016 demonstrated. However, pricing water at the cost of supplying it (allowing for constant reinvestment) with higher volume tariffs for industry, and subsidies for those who cannot afford to pay the economic cost, is possible for national supplies of water (Lahn, 2016).

Groundwater is more difficult to control and price. Moreover, there is limited knowledge of groundwater resources. UNESCWA commissioned the most comprehensive study to date in which the Arab countries participated (UN-ESCWA et al. 2013). This demonstrated the limits of data and while there are some bilateral agreements between countries over groundwater, few are operationalized (often hindered by conflict) (UN-ESCWA 2018). Even relative successes such as the Al-Saq-Disi agreement between Jordan and Saudi Arabia in 2015 have not fully resolved tensions.

Priorities for adaptation to future challenges in water management are:

- Scale back or abandon projects and industrial plans that are wasteful or polluting of water (e.g. Toshka)
- Water use per capita should be brought down to less wasteful levels – particularly by targeting high users such as industry, the commercial sector and large villas. Economic pricing of water will be the most important tool in achieving this goal but other steps such as the repair of distribution networks, education and public information campaigns are also essential. Improving water delivery infrastructure and irrigation efficiency are obvious areas that still have much potential to offer.
- International cooperation among MENA countries in the management of transboundary rivers and aquifers. This would require a change in attitudes from zero-sum-game to win-win. Regional cooperation is challenging, given the weakness of regional institutions, so cooperation at sub-regional and technical level should be pursued where possible. The potential for climate threats may also be an impetus for regional cooperation, for example between the GCC and Iran and between the countries sharing the River Nile.
- Increasing the use of non-conventional water resources such as wastewater re-use and investigating infrastructure that could capture heavy rainfall. In Oman for example, there are experiments with using stormwater for groundwater-recharge. This will need to be balanced with natural runoff that brings nutrients to the coast, but offers several co-benefits. Wastewater re-use is not a simple matter: it requires additional infrastructure, a high level of organisation and effective regulation and monitoring to prevent disease, among both farm-workers and consumers. A successful example is As-Samra waste-water treatment plant, which treats 100 million m³ annually meeting 80% of its energy demand through its own biogas digester and hydraulic turbines. This is reported to cover almost 10% of farming requirements in Jordan, equivalent to 10,000 hectares irrigated (Millenium Challenge Corporation 2018).

Food security and rural livelihoods

Food security can be understood in a much broader light than keeping the shelves stocked. In a time of climate change, planning for food security becomes more

complex. It needs to be tackled in a comprehensive way, taking into account unsustainable water withdrawal, higher temperatures *and* the potential for international food price spikes.

The strongest recommendations from expert interviews were: “Strengthen preparedness of the agriculture sector” and “coordinate food export policies and agricultural planning”. Planning requires greater awareness amongst food producers, weather and early warning systems, as well as insurance to help protect against drought. Drought-resistant varieties are part of the picture, alongside regenerative practices which are likely to be context-specific, require a long-term outlook and strong farmer engagement. For example, an option for wheat growing countries like Tunisia could be to introduce more barley that has lower water requirements, (Knaepen, 2021). Shifting to the use of organic fertiliser (which has better water retention properties) and permaculture techniques (which reduce water and chemical inputs and replenish soils) would benefit many farmers. Heatwaves will also affect animals, so protective measures such as growing indigenous trees and adding solar cooling systems in barns and shade netting may be needed (as a UNFCCC report on adaptation to climate change in Palestine suggests (Smithers et al. 2016)). All of the above would require some forms of financial support, awareness raising and extension services.

National planning may also benefit from cross border cooperation, especially between riparians, to make sure for example that dams are not filled while farmers are planting their crops – particularly important for Iraq and Egypt.

Food security policies should make provision for:

- nutrition for all, which means tackling malnutrition and obesity and thus dietary habits. This will have added macro-economic benefits in relieving pressure on the health system and increasing robustness to disease
- affordability - the cost of food relative to people’s incomes
- welfare and social safety nets that enable the poorest to have access to food staples
- invigorating rural livelihoods and thus limiting rural to urban migration
- the price and environmental costs of agricultural inputs
- achieving resilience through the right balance of locally produced and imported foodstuffs – and linked to that, establishing reliable supply chains and storage
- reducing and limiting food waste and where possible, turning discarded food into compost to return nutrients to the soil

Regeneration and remediation of landscapes

Much stronger environmental regulation and/or enforcement of that regulation is urgently needed in most of the region. This is all but impossible in countries undergoing conflict, while in countries lacking recourse to justice, elite land confiscation and projects that go ahead without proper environmental impact assessments are serious impediments to natural capital.

Ecosystem restoration is at an early stage in the region, although national conservation areas in Lebanon and Jordan show how this can be effective in nurturing threatened species and in encouraging tourism. There are also a range of experiences from across the Mediterranean region from ecological restoration of rivers in Spain to

restoring natural pastures in Egypt (IUCN 2019). Ambitious plans for larger scale tree-planting projects in Jordan and the Arabian Peninsula also pose entry points for work on landscape and ecosystem restoration (Kayed 2020).

It is increasingly clear that nature-based solutions such as the use of reedbeds for treating water in Oman and restoring natural coastal barriers like mangroves in Eastern Saudi Arabia will have economic benefits. The UAE is planning a major initiative to do this using drones to seed them along coastlines for example. However, currently governments will not always understand these projects to make economic sense. There are a number of areas in which the EU could engage in line with its own focus on mainstreaming natural capital accounting (European Commission 2021a). The EU helped to develop and supports the United Nations' System of Economic Environmental Accounting (SEEA) launched in March 2021. This aims to enable the contributions of forests, oceans and other ecosystems—to complement existing economic accounts (UN Statistical Commission 2021). This would be a rich area to explore with countries in the MENA region, especially those transitioning from dependence on oil rents and wanting to attract investment in green growth and eco-tourism.

Built infrastructure resilience

All countries – especially those planning major expansions of urban and industrial areas, will need to rapidly adopt a 'systems of systems' approach to planning new developments, resource use and management (land-use, mobility, water, energy, waste etc.) that takes both sustainability of resources and climate resilience into consideration in line with projections to 2100. In particular, the following is needed:

- More stringent regulation and enforcement of building restrictions on low-lying land and natural floodplains (wadis) and changing practices and mindset in the local planning and construction industry of how to build in harmony with the natural environment.
- Drainage and sewerage for coastal urban areas. This would be a more durable and environmentally sound approach than more dams to control water flow upstream. With more frequent extreme precipitation events, there is the opportunity to benefit from widespread drainage both to increase safety and to enable rainwater harvesting.
- Buildings retrofitting for adequate weatherization with particular attention to low income and dilapidated housing and public buildings such as schools and hospitals where upgrading using for example trombe walls, reflective and green roofs, sloping roofs (where heavy flooding is expected), rainwater collection, solar water heaters, solar panels and green could generate a range of co-benefits for immediate wellbeing while improving long-term resilience to climate change.
- Long-term planning to protect utilities given the vulnerability of energy and water supplies (particularly problems with water connection for local people suffering from a lack of water connection for several weeks in some regions after cyclones).
- Improving public awareness and the knowledge of the local people about climate change through education.

- Improving capacity building and development of skills through sharing experiences. Networks of technical expertise on these issues will enable learning from countries that have suffered similar flooding phenomenon, particularly in terms of watercourse and disaster management.

Adapting to much higher temperatures

Many urban areas in the region have grown in an unplanned way (Dammam in Saudi Arabia provides an example (Abou-Korin 2011)). Regeneration of these towns and cities – which will be necessary in coming decades for reasons of growing populations, dilapidating infrastructure and weatherization – should involve the retrofitting and reconfiguration (and in some cases reconstruction) of existing urban infrastructure to increase shading and make it easier to protect residents and workers from much higher temperatures. Humidity (wet bulb) is a greater threat than temperature rises, given the effects on the human body; projections and early warning systems can help warn people when to stay inside. At the same time, regeneration should be used to sensitively shift infrastructure and residential areas away from coastal zones that are threatened by sea-level rise and rising wet-bulb temperatures Bolleter et. al. 2021 make a strong case for this in the case of urban areas in the UAE. In exposed coastal areas, incentives for people to move inland over a longer period of time will be cheaper and less destabilizing than sudden mass relocation.

The EU's Role

During the 25 years since the Barcelona Process, the EU has strengthened its relationships with several countries in the MENA region and intends to increase its interaction on climate resilience and sustainability issues in line with the EU Green Deal. Clean energy and energy efficiency, sustainable agriculture, food-water-energy nexus models, circular economy and nature conservation and the use of digitalization as a tool of achieving these ends are all on the agenda.

While experts consulted for this report generally felt that the EU was focusing on the right areas in the region, there appeared to be room to make sure that the EU's planning was joined up and coordinated with other UN initiatives in the region. The EU 'being in it for the long-term' was valued. "The consistency and follow up - this has been really dramatic in making sure you have a lasting change instead of just jumping in and giving money."²⁰

Specific recommendations for the EU

7. There are strong opportunities for the EU as a major trading partner to the region to push for regional peace and cooperation through alignment with its Green Deal. This could include financing instruments to support businesses and build the necessary infrastructure, and the geopolitical level support to foster the diplomatic political will of parties to come to the table.
8. Assistance with planning for hazards is clearly needed, especially at the local level. The EU can provide Climate Change modelling tools for national and local scenario building. Early warning systems for all natural hazards is another area which others are already engaging in but there is much to do. One recommendation from Jordan was to support "farmer field schools" that

²⁰ Expert interviews, March 2021.

support people-centered learning and research to join up local observation and enhance the national picture of climate and environmental change. The specific use of Copernicus, the EU's Earth observation programme, could help enable countries to monitor climate change impacts, especially on land cover and land use (Abdelraouf, 2019).

9. Increasing humanitarian crises in which degraded environment and climate change worsen life prospects are already a reality in the region. The environment has tended to be a neglected part of the response to the Syria crisis. Finding ways in which remedial and post-conflict rehabilitation work can help address humanitarian needs whilst fostering long term environmental resilience is urgently needed. This could include, for example, leading a full environmental assessment of conditions in Northeastern Syria and parts of Iraq and supporting local action to clean up soil and water remediation (Wijnenberg et al, 2021).
10. Building climate resilience in cities and subnational areas of the MENA region by developing technical capacity to address climate related issues and manage water-energy-food (WEF) nexus. A forthcoming case study on cities in this series recommends that regional partners such as the EU adopt whole systems thinking at the urban scale rather than ad hoc projects.²¹ This requires supporting local capacity building and inclusive governance - especially at the municipal and community levels, increasing EU climate funding for WEF sectors in cities, and including city networks to support peer to peer climate action knowledge exchange as part of the EU's Green Deal diplomacy in the Southern Neighbourhood. As one regional expert put it "Work with municipalities can become a successful entry point if it can be sustained and supported and solution oriented."
11. Value for money requires close attention to good governance and the mechanisms to scale up sustainable finance. The way that funds are disbursed must take into account the effectiveness of centralized bureaucracies versus local agencies and other actors in the area concerned. One regional expert pointed out that EU funds pooled into a system for the Lebanese government had "led to more corruption". On the other hand, there are cases, particularly in conflict-affected areas with reconstruction needs, where a pragmatic, imperfect, approach will be needed in order to do anything at all.
12. Financial instruments used to build climate resilience can also help to empower local actors and build better national to sub-national linkages. The EU could, for example, help to scale up successful projects whereby NGOs have accessed small grants, through linking them up with the necessary authorities for continued support or making follow up funding conditional on effective implementation of a co-created plan. Encouraging moves to enable municipalities to be able to take on and manage capital to pursue resilience and adaptation strategies (as the GAM does), could also enable effective decentralization.

²¹ This forthcoming paper for CASCADDES has the working title: Climate Resilience in MENA Cities: Opportunities for the EU Green Deal.

Appendix .

Future scenarios

Given the difficulty of factoring in both technological advances that might change the picture beyond 2035 and the multiple international responses to climate change itself, these scenarios are imagined to run through from 2025 to 2035 and then evolve from there on to 2050. They are based on factors that interviewees expected to be most important in affecting the severity of climate impacts. However, they are not extensive. Climate change itself will of course interact with these factors but the idea is to consider factors generally external to climate change at this point.

Figure 17: Directional political scenarios for the MENA region 2025 - 2035

Scenario 1: 'Stagnation'

Worsening - Authoritarianism and conflicts

Regional dynamics in the Middle East and North Africa

Tensions are rising

This scenario is marked by increasing ethno-religious tensions across the region in a context of long-running conflicts.

States remain militarily strong with centralized bureaucracies

Lack of strategy to address long-term issues like border security, food and water security, or climate change. Governance is marked in general by centralized government control with increased authoritarian rule. This allows little room for civil society and reduces inclusion, accountability and transparency. Although moderate

bureaucratic efficacy is achieved, economies remain generally rent-based, dominated by state-backed business and large foreign corporate investments. Climate change questions are addressed rhetorically with reactive action and vanity projects rather than long-term planning for climate change impacts in most countries. In most cases, climate change (adaptation) plans and strategies are limited to a country level rather than a regional level. Moreover, end users are not well engaged in the development of climate change plans.

Antagonistic relations and competition inhibit greater integration

Some regional cooperation exists for instance through the East-Med Energy Forum, but generally antagonistic relations stymie attempts at greater integration of trade. High food import dependence continues and increases overall. No real cooperation is achieved between riparians and relations are marked by lack of trust and blame without concrete and defined rights and laws.

The wealth gap is rising and education stagnates

Some pockets of affluence remain and increase but there is a rising wealth gap alongside high population growth. With urbanization new types of crime and violence also emerge in cities. With little attention to education, there is a rising gap between state and private education. Awareness of climate change strengthens in some parts of the society but conspiracy theories are rife. Economic well-being: balances of trade worsen, debt is rising and jobs are created but under-employment is common.

International context: Internationally, a jolting energy transition and increased energy security policies in major importing countries create volatile to lower oil rents over time. The US retracts from the region and it and other powers provide some uncoordinated and ad-hoc aid and security packages. Food price shocks occur sporadically globally with overall higher food costs for the region. Lower than expected global finance is available due to failing international economic systems.

Scenario 2: 'Fragmentation'

Regional dynamics

States are fragmenting

This scenario is marked by greater fragmentation of states, the rise of new actors (e.g brokers/middle-men, military and paramilitary groups, elite groups) and uncoordinated decentralization of power, where transfer of power to local authorities does not happen. Simmering tensions do not allow much greater integration of trade. Food import dependence remains high.

Governance is a mixed picture

Some breakaway regions are supported to improve capacities while others become more feudal. There is greater power for the elite and for the private sector in some areas such as in the energy and agri-food sectors, but less room for the private sector in others.

An imperfect peace with sporadic migration

An 'imperfect peace' exists between groups and countries sharing rivers. There is mixed population growth with some countries' populations reducing due to conflict

and migration and others increasing. Black markets are growing in some places and more porous borders mean increased illegal transfer of goods, and trafficking of humans and drugs.

Increasing divides in economic well-being

Awareness of climate change is stronger and some climate adaptation strategies take shape but inter-group tensions and fragmentation inhibit effective and long-term implementation. Increasing divide between private, religious and state educated groups in society. Balance of trade is similar but mixed. Jobs are created mainly in the informal economy and black market.

International context: Internationally, the US exhibits increased interest in tactical diplomacy in the region, vying with other powers, China and Russia. Energy transition coupled with constraints on production in some places create volatile to medium oil prices. Increased strategic investment by other powers and responsive aid; climate resilience focused finance and packages make possible some projects. Food prices are volatile with some price spikes.

Scenario 3: 'Cooperation'

Gradual peace-making / Sustainability, stability and equality

Regional dynamics:

Gradual peace-making and stability

This scenario is marked by a gradual decrease in conflict and greater attention to cooperative, diplomatic solutions in the region. This in turn enables increased investment, finance and technology innovation and adoption.

Strengthening institutions and decentralization

There is stronger commitment to institutional governance and diversification pathways. The state system continues but with greater decentralization of authority to local governments, one of the conditions to effective local adaptation. A vibrant private sector and greater flourishing of entrepreneurship is enabled by increased rule of law, regulation and clear market incentives.

Increasing cooperation

Basin management between riparians is more cooperative, with more focus on the needs and capacities of communities and ecosystem restoration. Food import dependence reduces as greater regional trade integration coupled with cooperative water management, and more investment in national diversified food production, increases sustainability.

An educational dividend

There is strong public awareness of climate change and environmental issues which find channels of expression through civil society groupings and are represented in political systems. Population growth reduces and there is greater attention to increasing educational quality and equality and investment. Balance of trade improves, debt reduces and jobs are increasingly provided by the private sector and universal income solves some of the problems of the move to automation.

International context: The international community strengthens with greater engagement of multiple parties cooperating over development and security with coordinated aid and finance including climate finance. Oil prices rise and then fall – a boom to bust period, as alternative technologies and regulations take hold. Food prices remain volatile to high with some shocks.

Table 3: Regional parameters

Parameter	Scenario 1 - Stagnation	Scenario 2 - Fragmentation	Scenario 3 - Cooperation
Stability level	Worsening – increasing tensions and ongoing armed conflict	Low-level but unresolved conflicts	Gradual peace-making
Governance	Medium efficacy bureaucratically but rigid and lacking in accountability and rule of law.	Less efficacy at national level but with some areas evolving new models of governance	Improving levels of accountability, competency and rule of law.
Ecological state	Worsening	Similar to today overall - better in some places, worsening in others	Improving
Economic well-being (trade balance, debt, employment)	Worsening trade balances, rising levels of indebtedness, high unemployment	Similar trade balances but with some areas failing, increase in black markets, trafficking and militarized economy	Improved trade balances, rising employment/universal basic income in some places, reducing debt
Local empowerment (the extent to which power is distributed and ability to make decisions)	Lower	High but uncoordinated	Increasing
Transboundary cooperation	Little – lower than today	Greater with new actors joining forces around specific eco-systems but with more parties involved and less ability for national coordination	Greater, with moves towards cooperative basin-wide management strategies
Regional trade integration	Similar to today	Small scale – a little more than today but increased through black and grey markets	Greater regional integration of food and materials trade
Population growth	High (similar to today)	Medium/mixed (lower than today in some countries, higher in others due to movement of peoples and continuing fertility rates)	Reducing, with more girls staying longer in education and delaying marriage.
Migration	High rural to urban migration, high urbanization, low cross border migration	Similar urban to rural migration, high cross border migration	Lower rural to urban and cross border migration
Public awareness (and activism) of environment and climate change	Similar	Stronger, but confused	Stronger, well informed
Quality and equality of education	Little attention to educational reform, increasing pressure on state schools – rising gap between private and state educated.	More fragmented education system with rise of different types of institution (religious, elite private and NGO-run schools)	Rising, with increased investment and attention to education at all levels. Reduced gap between state and private education.

International parameters

Geopolitical relations – esp US interest (but could be other major power)	Reduced interest from major powers	Tactical major power diplomacy, multipower interests,	Strengthened and more aligned engagement of multiple parties
International engagement including on aid and finance (all powers)	Reduced investment and adhoc, uncoordinated aid and finance efforts	Responsive aid efforts, increased strategic efforts but lack of coordination	Increased investment in and cooperation over development and security
International food prices	Volatile food prices with some shocks and generally higher prices	Volatile food prices with some shocks and generally higher prices	Volatile food prices with some shocks and generally higher prices
International oil prices	Volatile to lower oil rents (average lower than 2010-2020 years)	Volatile to medium oil prices (similar to 2010-2020)	Boom period followed by terminal decline of oil prices

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